

D2.2

PoDIUM platform requirements and specifications

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547
Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Work package	WP2 – Requirements and specifications
Deliverable number	D2.2 PoDIUM platform requirements and specifications
Status - version, date	V1.3, 07/07/2023
Deliverable leader	LINKS
Contractual date of delivery	30/06/2023
Keywords	Platform requirements; components; interfaces

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Harilaos Vasiliadis	AAE	26/06/2022
Peer review 2	Manolo Serrano, Manolo Vivo, Rafael Peris	ETRA	26/06/2022

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
01	07/10/2022	John Sebastian	First draft of document structure + chapter 1 introduction, 2 approach of 3 thematic areas
02	28/04/2023	Guido Gavilanes, Daniele Brevi	First ToC
03	10/05/2023	Guido Gavilanes	Draft initial values for requirements from partners
04	17/05/2023	Guido Gavilanes, Filippo Visintainer	Definitions for functional and non-functional requirements.
06	24/05/2023	Andrea Vesco	Integration of Cyber Security contribution
07	31/05/2023	Guido Gavilanes	Integration of all first contributions from partners
10	07/06/2023	Guido Gavilanes	Integration of all complete contributions from partners and methodology
11	16/06/2023	Guido Gavilanes, Edoardo Bonetto,	Addition of new paragraphs in methodology, introduction, definitions and some corrections

		Daniele Brevi, Filippo Visintainer	Version shared for peer review
12	28/06/2023	Guido Gavilanes	Integration of changes proposed by reviewers
13	07/07/2023	Lazaros Gkatzikis	Proof-reading and rephrasing to improve readability

Legal Disclaimer

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority, CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that it is fit for any specific purpose. The PoDIUM project Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Copyright © PoDIUM Consortium, 2022.

Table of contents

- Quality Control..... 2
- Version History 2
- Legal Disclaimer 3
- List of Figures 7
- List of Tables 7
- List of abbreviations and acronyms..... 9
- Executive Summary..... 11**
- 1. Introduction 12**
 - 1.1. Project introduction 12
 - 1.2. Purpose of the deliverable 12
 - 1.3. Intended audience..... 12
 - 1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables 13
- 2. PoDIUM integrated ecosystem..... 14**
 - 2.1. PoDIUM platform 14
 - 2.1.1. CAVs 14
 - 2.1.2. Networking..... 14
 - 2.1.3. Computing entities and road-side infrastructure 14
 - 2.2. CCAM messaging 14
 - 2.3. Security, trust, privacy..... 15
 - 2.3.1. Data and data source reliability 16
- 3. Requirements methodology..... 17**
 - 3.1. Platform requirements sources..... 17
 - 3.1.1. Standards and recommendations 17
 - 3.1.2. Consortiums 18
 - 3.1.3. Other public documents..... 18
 - 3.2. Identified use case categories 18
- 4. Platform use-case-specific requirements..... 19**
 - 4.1. UC1 – Cooperative corridor management in city of Ulm..... 19
 - 4.1.1. Functional requirements 19
 - 4.1.2. Non-functional requirements..... 20
 - 4.1.2.1. CAVs..... 20

- 4.1.2.2. Networking 21
- 4.1.2.3. Computing entities 21
- 4.2. UC2 – PDI for user-centric, CCAM-enabled traffic management in urban corridors with high priority vehicles and VRUs 22
 - 4.2.1. Functional requirements 22
 - 4.2.2. Non-functional Requirements 29
 - 4.2.2.1. CAVs 29
 - 4.2.2.2. Networking 29
 - 4.2.2.3. Computing entities 30
- 4.3. UC3 – Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled traffic management in the Mediterranean cross-border corridor 31
 - 4.3.1. Functional requirements 31
 - 4.3.2. Non-functional requirements 40
 - 4.3.2.1. CAVs 40
 - 4.3.2.2. Networking 41
 - 4.3.2.3. Computing entities 41
- 4.4. UC4 – Trusted cooperative perception for intersection manoeuvre assistance 43
 - 4.4.1. Functional requirements 43
 - 4.4.2. Non-functional Requirements 46
 - 4.4.2.1. CAVs 46
 - 4.4.2.2. Networking 47
 - 4.4.2.3. Computing Entities 47
- 4.5. UC5 – Risk management in a highway tunnel 48
 - 4.5.1. Functional requirements 48
 - 4.5.2. Non-functional requirements 51
 - 4.5.2.1. CAVs 51
 - 4.5.2.2. Networking 52
 - 4.5.2.3. Computing entities 52

5. Platform requirements 53

- 5.1. Functional Common Platform Requirements 53
- 5.2. Non-functional common platform requirements 54
 - 5.2.1. CAVs 54
 - 5.2.2. Networking 55
 - 5.2.3. Computing entities 55
- 5.3. Requirements for CCAM Messages 56
 - 5.3.1. General CCAM Message Requirements 56
 - 5.3.2. Use case-specific CCAM message requirements 57
 - 5.3.2.1. Use Case 2 57
 - 5.3.2.2. Use Case 3 57
 - 5.3.2.3. Use Case 4 57

5.3.2.4. Use Case 5.....	58
5.3.3. CCAM Message Security.....	58
5.4. Requirements for trust, security and privacy.....	58
5.4.1. Trusted computing approach.....	58
5.4.2. Data and Data Source Reliability approach.....	64
6. Conclusions.....	66
7. References.....	67
8. Annex: Classification of networking vehicular use case categories related to PODIUM.....	68
8.1. Road safety.....	68
8.1.1. Requirements of use cases related to static information.....	68
8.1.2. Requirements of use cases related to dynamic information.....	69
8.2. Cooperative driving.....	69
8.2.1. Manoeuvres coordination.....	69
8.2.2. Cooperative Manoeuvres Coordination requirements.....	69
8.2.3. Platooning requirements.....	70
8.2.4. Tele-operated driving.....	71
8.3. Sensors sharing requirements.....	72
8.4. Traffic management.....	73

List of Figures

Figure 1: UC2 - Functional Requirements – Scenarios: SCN1	28
Figure 2: UC2 - Platform Functional Requirements – Scenarios: SCN2.....	28
Figure 3: UC2 - Functional requirements – Scenarios: SCN3	28
Figure 4 UC3 - Functional requirements – Scenario: SCN1	39
Figure 5 UC3 - Functional Requirements – Scenario: SCN2	40
Figure 6: UC4 - Functional Requirements – Scenarios: Give way, stop and wait, passthrough, prevented start, collision avoidance	45
Figure 7: UC4 - Platform Functional Requirements – Scenario: Attestation.....	46
Figure 8: UC2 - Platform functional requirements – Scenario: Risk maintenance.....	51
Figure 9: Chain of automotive attestation	60
Figure 10 : Software Integrity Architecture.....	63
Figure 11: Basic procedure of building a Chain of Trust.	64

List of Tables

Table 1 Use Case Categories	18
Table 2 Functional Requirements – FunctionalityTable 1 Use Case Categories	19
Table 3: UC1 – Functional Requirements – Scenarios: CAV Passing Lane Blockage and VRU Passing Lane Blockage.....	20
Table 4: UC1 – Non- functional CAV requirements.....	21
Table 5: UC1 – Non-functional networking requirements	21
Table 6: UC1 – Number of computing entities.....	22
Table 7: UC2 – Functional requirements.....	22
Table 8: UC2 – Functional Requirements – All scenarios	23
Table 9: UC2 – CAV non-functional requirements	29
Table 10: UC2 – Non-functional networking requirements	30
Table 11: UC2 – Number of computing entities.....	30
Table 12 UC3 - Functional Requirements – Functionality	31
Table 13 UC3- Functional Requirements – both scenarios	32
Table 14 UC3 – CAV and CV requirements.....	40
Table 15 UC3 – networking requirements	41
Table 16 UC3 – number of computing entities	41
Table 17: UC4 – Functional Requirements – Functionality	43
Table 18: UC4 – Functional Requirements – Scenarios: Give way, stop and wait, passthrough, prevented start, collision avoidance	43
Table 19: UC4 – Functional Requirements – Scenario: Attestation	46
Table 20: UC4 – CAV non-functional requirements	47

Table 21: UC4 Networking Requirements 47

Table 22: UC4 – number of computing entities 48

Table 23: UC5 – Functionality Table..... 48

Table 24: UC5 – Functional requirements – All scenarios..... 48

Table 25: UC5 – Non-functional CAV requirements..... 51

Table 26: UC5 – Non-functional Network requirements 52

Table 27: UC5 – number of computing entities 52

Table 28: Platform Functional Requirements 53

Table 29: Non-functional CAV Platform requirements 54

Table 30: Non-functional networking platform requirements..... 55

Table 31: Non-functional Computing Entities platform requirements 55

Table 32: General CCAM message requirements..... 56

Table 33: UC2 CCAM message requirements..... 57

Table 34: UC3 CCAM message requirements..... 57

Table 35: UC4 CCAM message requirements..... 57

Table 36: UC5 CCAM message requirements..... 58

Table 37: CCAM message security requirements..... 58

Table 38 Trust and Security Requirements 60

Table 39 TCB Trust and Security Requirements 61

Table 40 Attestor Trust and Security Requirements..... 61

Table 41 RSUs and OBUs' Trust and Security Requirements..... 62

Table 42 Application Data Security 62

Table 43 Data and data source reliability - Approach 1 64

Table 44 Data and data source reliability - Approach 2 65

Table 45: Communication requirements for the different use cases categories..... 73

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
ADAS	Automated Driving Assistance System
AIC	Artificial Incidents Camera
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Automated Programming Interface
CAV	Connected Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CIAA	Confidentiality Integrity Availability Authenticity
CRE	Collision Risk Estimator
CV	Connected Vehicle
C-V2X	Cellular vehicle-to-everything (LTE-PC5)
CVM	Connected Vehicle Manager
DT	Digital Twin
EV	Emergency Vehicle
EVM	Emergency Vehicle Manager
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
LL	Living Lab
MAPEM	MAP Extended Message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
OBU	On-Board Unit
ODD	Operational Design Domain
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
RSU	Road-Side Unit
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SPU	Sensor Processing Unit
TL	Traffic Light
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TMS	Traffic Management System

UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
VRUM	VRU Manager

Executive Summary

This document has a three-fold objective, namely i) to describe the general requirements of the PoDIUM platform and the specific requirements of its main components, ii) to specify the requirements of C-ITS Messages concerning the PoDIUM Use Cases (UC) and iii) to analyse the security requirements and create the software integrity architecture.

The document classifies the derived requirements in two main categories, namely functional and non-functional. Functional requirements represent specify the necessary functionality and interactions that would allow the use cases to achieve their respective goals. The term non-functional requirements, is used to describe the requirements that ensure the correct operation of the PODIUM components in the system, e.g., performance, operation conditions or scalability requirements. Finally, a set of the common/general platform requirements is presented, which applies to the PODIUM platform and describes the common functionality expected also in related CCAM systems.

Besides, the CCAM messages requirements are presented as they constitute an integral part of the PoDIUM approach, organised as common and use case specific requirements.

Regarding the Trust, Security and privacy requirements, they are focused on the areas of trusted computing (as security strategy) and data source reliability with two defined approaches to increase the data trust and truthfulness of the data used in the use cases where these approaches will be applied.

The specification of the requirements resulted from direct surveys with the UC leaders and all the involved PoDIUM partners, along with a thorough investigation of the more general and well-known use case types present in the literature for the identification of the necessary functionality.

These deliverable states a starting point to the specifications leading to the development of the architecture in the WP3 and further integration and data collection carried out in WP4.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of this document is to identify the system requirements of the PODIUM project. It is the joint outcome of Task 2.2, Task 2.3 and Task 2.4 in which the requirements and specifications were defined.

In particular, the requirement identification process is addressed in three main domains: Connected Automated Vehicles (CAVs), networking, and computing entities. The report describes the methodologies and the approach used to identify the system requirements. The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

1.3. Intended audience

This deliverable is intended for public use from the ninth month of the project. It sets also basic definitions that will be used in WP3 – Technical Innovation and Development.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable describes in Section 2 the PoDIUM integrated system that includes the different platform components and their domains, as well as the CCAM messages and the security, trust and privacy aspects considered within PODIUM. The methodology to identification of requirements is explained in Section 3, while Section 4 widely describes the results of the requirement identification for each use case in all domains. Section 5 dedicates space to common requirements identified across all use cases. Finally, Section 6 concludes this deliverable with final considerations.

The references used in the document are presented in Section 7. Section 8 contains an annex that describes the method used for the derivation of initial networking requirements based on existing bibliography analysis.

2. PoDIUM integrated ecosystem

The PoDIUM integrated ecosystem comprises all the aspects that enable the PoDIUM PDI to offer CCAM services. This ecosystem includes the PoDIUM platform that is made by the CAVs, the networking, the computing entities and the road-side infrastructure. Further essential actors that are involved in providing or in using the PDI developed in PoDIUM. The CCAM Messaging and Security, Trust, and Privacy are further fundamental topics that need to be considered when specifying the PoDIUM Platform requirements.

2.1. PoDIUM platform

For better organization of work, the PODIUM platform has been divided into its constituting components, namely Connected Automated Vehicle (CAV), road-side infrastructure, cellular and short-range networking, and cloud/edge computing entities. Since cellular networking and short-range networking are related with the road-side equipment, they have been grouped together. Road-side units have also computing capabilities, e.g. hosting attestation protocols or an acting as an intermediate step in perception functionality. These observations lead to the consideration of the three domains described below; CAVs, networking and computing entities.

2.1.1. CAVs

CAVs are the main consumers of the data provided by the platform. Moreover, CAVs interact with Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) typically for safety purposes. The consortium has identified actuation, decision and communications as the main functionalities of CAVs. In brief, CAVs, as road users, use PDI-provided information for decisions and further actuation.

2.1.2. Networking

Networking covers the connectivity/communication functionalities that allow CAVs and other connected devices either to provide data to the PoDIUM platform or to retrieve information generated by the platform. Networking covers both the uplink and downlink, from devices or sensors to cloud/edge (potentially via an RSU) and from cloud/edge services to CAVs and/or other road users.

2.1.3. Computing entities and road-side infrastructure

Given the considerations made at the beginning of this subsection, road-side infrastructure has a dual role and fits into the cellular and short-range networking domain and also to the computing entities. In the latter case, the road-side infrastructure often fuses together data from multiple sensors present on the road side.

2.2. CCAM messaging

CCAM messages are used to communicate among CAVs and between a CAV and the infrastructure. The messages used are standardized and known as C-ITS Messages within the community. CCAM messages in PoDIUM will either use the existing message specifications (typically as defined by the

ETSI TC ITS group) or extend the standard messages to cover the needs of the PoDIUM use cases. PoDIUM partners are indeed exploring the definition of new messages for UC-specific purposes and will provide feedback to the relevant ETSI groups.

The CCAM messages for the different use cases are described in Section 5.3. It provides a first insight into the messages used and defines the basis for future development within the use cases. Furthermore, it harmonizes the messages with the existing standards and specifications.

2.3. Security, trust, privacy

Traditionally, the security of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) includes the pillars of confidentiality, integrity, availability, and authentication referred to as the CIAA pillars.

- Confidentiality refers to the requirement that sensitive, critical system information and data are not perceivable by parties who are not the intended recipients.
- Integrity refers to the requirement that an unauthorized entity cannot corrupt or modify sensitive data or information. Moreover, it involves the requirement that data received is not different than what was originally intended to be sent.
- Availability refers to the requirement any legitimate element of the system can access requested information; an obvious subversion on availability is a Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack.
- Authentication refers to the requirement that communicating elements can verify the identity of each other and they are only able to access to information corresponding to their access level.

To ensure these pillars among communicating elements of ITS several practice and standards has been defined, *e.g.*,

- ETSI TS 102 940 V2.1.1 (2021-07) on ITS communications security architecture and management,
- ETSI TS 103 601 V1.1.1 (2020-10) on the security management messages communication requirements and distribution protocols,
- ETSI TS 103 097 V2.1.1 (2021-10) on the security header and certificate formats,
- ETSI TS 102 731 V2.0.0 (2022-11) on the security services,
- ETSI TS 103 600 V1.2.1 (2022-02) on the interoperability tests for security,
- ETSI TS 102 943 V2.0.0 (2022-11) and ETSI TS 102 942 V2.0.0 (2022-11) on access control and confidentiality service respectively, and
- ETSI TS 102 941 V2.2.1 (2022-11) on trust and privacy management.

PoDIUM aims to establish and demonstrate an extended level of security, interoperable with the practices highlighted before, and based on the adoption of the principles of Trusted Computing (TC). TC is a set of interoperable technologies to achieve a level of trust regarding the behaviour of a device. The core element of TC is the hardware Root of Trust called Trusted Platform Module (TPM), a tamper-resistant cryptographic hardware integrated with the system board that implements primitive cryptographic functions on top of which more complex features can be built following TCG specification TPM 2.0 [1].

The objective of TC is to enable devices to measure and prove their integrity cryptographically, i.e., prove to the other devices involved in the network that their running software is the intended one and

it has not been tampered with. PoDIUM intends to explore how to apply TC to C-ITS for the purpose of building trust among critical devices (*e.g.*, OBU, RSU, MEC Servers) and avoid exchange of incorrect or malicious information over secure C-ITS protocols, as detailed in Section 5.4.

2.3.1. Data and data source reliability

CAVs benefit from the information provided by sensors and other data sources described in the PODIUM use cases. They receive that information via CCAM messages, generated by the platform using the data available and contributed constantly from a wide variety of sensors; CCAM messages are generated using different decision points varying from case to case, but the decisions are as valid as the data supporting those decisions. Thus, the raw data collected by the PODIUM architecture will result to good decisions only if they are certain and true.; the truthfulness of the data plays an important role in PODIUM; two approaches to it are conceived to specify at the end of section 5.4.

3. Requirements methodology

In order to establish the taxonomy of the requirements identified in this document, it is necessary to explain the terms functional and non-functional requirements, and they are also related to the component domain.

- The term non-functional requirements, is used to describe the requirements that ensure the correct operation of the PODIUM components in the system, e.g., performance, operating conditions or scalability requirements.
- functional requirements represent a first step in specifying the functionality required from the system and interactions that allow the use cases to achieve their respective goals.

Regarding the specification of the non-functional networking requirements has been based on the analysis of a wide set of use cases related to the CCAM vertical. The identification of the use cases was based on several sources that are introduced in Section 3.1. The use cases have been grouped in different categories, that are introduced in Section 3.2, and the PoDIUM use cases were associated to these categories. The analysis of the needs of these use cases was the starting point for the elicitation of the PoDIUM requirements. Non-functional requirements for CAV and computing entities were identified by direct survey since there were no well-known use cases as in the case of the CCAM vertical.

In parallel, the consortium performed an extended analysis of the PoDIUM components, the basic PoDIUM functionalities and their interactions for every UC based on the results of D2.1. The result was a set of functional requirements capturing the interactions of the PoDIUM components. Interaction diagrams were derived to illustrate these interactions.

Then, these requirements have been clustered together to create two sets of requirements, namely the common PoDIUM platform requirements and the use-case specific requirements. The network requirements that have been derived from the UC analysis are reported in the Annex.

3.1. Platform requirements sources

The requirements specification has considered all relevant sources of information, such as technical reports and specifications from standardization bodies, documentation made available from relevant associations and consortiums, and other public documents from European research projects and other initiatives in the CCAM field. Eventually, the requirements have been mainly derived based on the knowledge and expertise of the by PoDIUM partners based on the system and UC analysis performed within the PoDIUM project.

3.1.1. Standards and recommendations

The most relevant standardization bodies were considered, namely 3GPP and ETSI. 3GPP Technical Reports 22.885 and 22.886 about V2X services [2,3] provided input for the identification of the use cases, while 3GPP Technical Specifications 22.185 and 22.186 [4,5] introduces network requirements for the identified V2X use cases. Compliance of the derived PoDIUM requirements with the ETSI Technical Report 102 638 [6], describing the basic set of applications of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), was also ensured.

3.1.2. Consortiums

The 5GAA Automotive Association has made publicly available two related technical reports [7,8] that describe several C-V2X UCs and introduce service level requirements of these UCs. A white paper from the CAR 2 CAR Communication Consortium has been also considered [9]. This white paper introduces the expected evolution of V2X services together with high level requirements

3.1.3. Other public documents

Other CCAM-related initiatives have been considered when specifying the details of the UCs and the requirements. In particular, documentation from the C-Roads Platform was analyzed. Inputs from deliverables of European research projects, such as 5GCroCo, were also considered.

The research expertise of the PoDIUM consortium partners was the main driving force for the definition of the requirements. The consortium members have used their previous experiences from research and testing on real products, and the previously identified best practices. Through collaborative analysis of the PoDIUM system and its UCs, we specified the requirements presented in this document, which can be reused in similar future projects, products or use cases.

3.2. Identified use case categories

According to our literature analysis, the networking domain has attracted much of the attention of the CCAM community; so every use case identified in the literature is characterized by its networking requirements. Based on our characterization, these are non-functional requirements in our use cases, since they are mostly related with performance and scalability of the PoDIUM approach, and they are not connected directly with the UC functionality. The non-functional networking requirements identified in our literature analysis are reported in the Annex.

Table 1 Use Case Categories

ID	Use Case Category	Summary
CD	Cooperative Driving	All cooperative manoeuvres such as cooperative overtaking, cooperative intersection crossing, platooning and cooperative lane merging. It covers the case of sharing sensor data
DC	Driver comfort	green light optimized speed advisory (GLOSA), parking information
DA	Driver-aware services	Events that are close-by and can be of interest to the driver. It uses information of how the driver is using the vehicle to provide other information such as in-vehicle entertainment, shops, etc
TM	Traffic management	Macroscopic traffic limitations due to pollution, alternate traffic flow routing due to roadworks or accidents.
IP	Road infrastructure planning	Long term traffic considerations to consider modifying road infrastructure
VM	Vehicle status monitoring	Monitoring for predictive maintenance and or training loops
RS	Road safety	Alerting the driver and/or the autonomous vehicle of some hazardous events. Detection of misbehaving driving

4. Platform use-case-specific requirements

For every use case, a list of functional requirements was produced, based on the identified functionality. All domains in the use cases have their associated functionalities; a list of functional requirements is included based on the interactions expected in every use case. Finally, a list of the non-functional requirements for every domain is derived and presented for all use cases.

4.1. UC1 – Cooperative corridor management in city of Ulm

4.1.1. Functional requirements

The use case comprises a cooperative corridor management in the city of Ulm and is composed of two scenarios. Both scenarios are centered around a CAV that approaches a blockage on its own lane. In the first scenario, the CAV passes this blockage using the opposite lane. To this end, information from the infrastructure (sensors connected to sensor processing units (SPUs)) and connected road users (baseline solution) or only connected road users (lightweight solution) is used at the MEC to build an environment model, also called digital twin (DT). This DT is then used by a cooperative planner on the MEC server to manage the corridor. This entails the following required functionalities of the road users, the infrastructure and the MEC in terms of sending and receiving information such as the position, the route for the road users, the environment model for the CAVs, as well as computing and distributing the digital twin and the cooperative maneuvers for the MEC. Finally, the CAV is required to react to the received digital twin and the cooperative maneuvers. The same requirements stand for the second scenario of a VRU passing the blockage on the non-blocked lane, where the cooperative planner instructs the CAV which is blocked behind the obstacle to pass after the VRU has passed.

Table 2 Functional Requirements – Functionality Table 1 Use Case Categories

Subsystem/entity	Functions (optional info: subfunctions included)
CAV	Digital Twin (sensing, data fusion, tracking) Planning (trajectory planning) Actuation Communication (encoding/decoding, dispatching, network, scheduling)
SPU	Perception Communication
RSU	Communication
MEC	Digital Twin (data fusion, tracking, truth assessment) Planning (cooperative maneuver planning) Communication (message generation, dispatching, scheduling)

Table 3: UC1 – Functional Requirements – Scenarios: CAV Passing Lane Blockage and VRU Passing Lane Blockage

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
PF_UC1-001	The CAV shall be able to send its environment model to the MEC.	CAV	Communication
PF_UC1-002	The CAV shall be able to send its position to the MEC.	CAV	Communication
PF_UC1-003	The VRU shall be able to send its position to the MEC.	CAV/MEC	Communication
PF_UC1-004	The SPU shall be able to send object detections to the MEC. This applies only to the second scenario and the baseline implementation of the first scenario.	RSU/MEC	Perception/Communication
PF_UC1-005	The MEC shall be able to fuse information from different sources to calculate/update the DT.	MEC	Digital Twin
PF_UC1-006	The MEC shall be able to plan cooperative maneuver based on the information of the DT.	MEC	Planning
PF_UC1-007	The CAV and VRU shall be able to send its route to the MEC.	CAV/MEC/VRU	Communication
PF_UC1-008	The MEC shall be able to send the DT (as CPM) to the CAV.	CAV/MEC	Communication
PF_UC1-009	The CAV and VRU shall be able to receive cooperative maneuver.	CAV/VRU	Communication
PF_UC1-010	The MEC shall be able to send the cooperative maneuver to the CAV and VRU.	MEC/CAV/VRU	Communication
PF_UC1-012	The CAV shall be able to send the DT (as CPM) to the MEC.	CAV/MEC	Communication
PF_UC1-013	The CAVs shall be able to react on received cooperative maneuver accordingly, limited to use case needs (e.g., overtaking, stopping).	CAV	Planning/Actuation

4.1.2. Non-functional requirements

4.1.2.1. CAVs

In this use case, two connected and automated vehicles perform a cooperative maneuver initiated by the MEC server. Therefore, two CAVs need to be available and must support communication to the

MEC server. UC1 investigates the effects of redundant communication paths between the involved entities. To evaluate these effects, at least one CAV needs to support different communication paths to the MEC server.

Table 4: UC1 – Non- functional CAV requirements

ID	Description	Supporting information or docs
PNF_UC1_CAV_001	Two connected and automated vehicles are available.	D2.1
PNF_UC1_CAV_002	The CAVs shall be able to communicate with the MEC server or or RSU via redundant paths	D2.1

4.1.2.2. Networking

The use case is based on the transmission of positions and routes from the road users, the environmental model of the CAVs as well as the detections of the infrastructure sensors. For the use case, moderate platform requirements in terms of latency and bandwidth are acceptable, as the exchanged message sizes or specifically flow rates are rather small and the message exchange frequency is moderate. The required platform reliability is high (as in 99%) to ensure that the information available for the digital twin and for the cooperative planner is complete and up to date.

Table 5: UC1 – Non-functional networking requirements

ID	Description	UC type
PNF_UC1-NET_001	platform should support latency of 200 ms between sensors/vehicles and edge	CD, RS
PNF_UC1-NET_002	platform should support a bandwidth of 1 Mbps between sensors/vehicles and edge	CD, RS
PNF_UC1-NET_003	platform should support Reliability of 99% between sensors/vehicles and edge	CD, RS

4.1.2.3. Computing entities

The use case considers two scenarios, where the first scenario is split to two cases (baseline and lightweight solution). In the baseline case of the first scenario, the computation of the digital twin and the subsequent calculation of the cooperative maneuver is based on the positions, environment model and detections obtained from the road users and the roadside infrastructure sensors. The edge entity supports the computation of the digital twin as well as the cooperative maneuver planning. Hence, the required number of computing entities in this scenario as displayed in the table below comprises an Edge entity, two CAVs and multiple (in this case seven) roadside infrastructure sensor entities that are connected using the different available communication technologies used in parallel for redundancy. The VRU passing the blockage scenario (scenario 2) includes in addition one VRU that uses a subset of available communication technologies. Further, the lightweight version of the first scenario dispenses with the infrastructure hence it aims to create the equivalent CAV passing obstacle scenario based only on the CAV supplied information.

Table 6: UC1 – Number of computing entities

Number of computing entities	Scenario 1a- CAV Passing Lane Blockage Baseline	Scenario 1b- CAV Passing Lane Blockage Lightweight	Scenario 2- VRU Passing Lane Blockage	Physical connections
Cloud	0	0	0	
Edge	1	1	1	2 LAN interfaces
Road-side	7	0	7	6x: 60-GHz Wifi, 5G FR1, ITS-G5 1x: LTE, 5G FR1 + FR2
VRU	0	0	1	5G FR1, 5G FR2, LTE+
Vehicle	2	2	2	60-GHz Wifi, 5G FR1, 5G FR2,ITS-G5, LTE+

4.2. UC2 – PDI for user-centric, CCAM-enabled traffic management in urban corridors with high priority vehicles and VRUs

This Use Case will be demonstrated in three scenarios:

- SCN1: connected Emergency Vehicles (EVs) are tracked for both enabling traffic management system (TMS) providing them priority at intersections with traffic lights, and informing CAVs and CVs so they can perform cooperative manoeuvres and facilitate the EV movement.
- SCN2: CAVs and CVs cooperate with the TMS acting as sensors that enable the production of useful traffic metrics (O-D matrices, travel times) and improve the capability for TMS assessing the status of the road network and executing optimal traffic strategies. In addition to this, the TMS shall provide CAVs and CVs with relevant information about the status of traffic and routing recommendations.
- SCN3: One or more Artificial Intelligence Camera (AIC) detect and follow trajectories of vulnerable road users (VRUs) near a crossing with risk of collision with CAV and CVs, and a Collision Risk Estimator (CRE) generates high risk of collision alerts that are sent to both the vehicles (CVs and CVAs) –that shall react accordingly, reducing their speed- and to the VRUs – that shall get a visual or sound alert via a wearable.

The present section first describes the functional requirements involved in this functionality. The non-functional requirements that specify other aspects that are required for network, CAVs and hardware and software components being able to support the functionality are described in section 4.2.2.

4.2.1. Functional requirements

Table 7: UC2 – Functional requirements

Subsystem/entity	Functions (optional info: subfunctions included)
AIC (Artificial Intelligence Camera)	Detection Communication Data fusion
CAV	Perception (sensing, V2X-based p., data fusion) Human Machine Interaction (Warning, recommendation, ODD inform)

(Connected Autonomous Vehicle)	Actuation (simulated via HMI) Communication (encoding/decoding, dispatching/receive, network)
CAV (Connected Vehicle)	Human Machine Interaction (Warning, recommendation, ODD inform) Communication (encoding/decoding, dispatching/receive, network)
EV (Emergency Vehicle)	Localization Communication
CVM (Connected Vehicle Manager)	Communication
EVM (Emergency Vehicle Manager)	Communication
TMS (Traffic Management System)	Data-fusion Decision Movement assist
CRE (Collision Risk Estimator)	Decision Movement assist
VRU-APP (Vulnerable Road User)	Localization Data fusion Actuation (simulated via HMI)
VRUM (VRU manager)	Communication

Table 8: UC2 – Functional Requirements – All scenarios

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
PF_UC2-AIC_001	AIC shall be able to detect VRUs in the video	AIC (CE)	Detection
PF_UC2-AIC_002	AIC shall be able to detect if VRUs are inside of a predefined dangerous area or not.	AIC (CE)	Detection
PF_UC2-AIC_003	AIC shall notify the CRE the detection of VRUs	AIC (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-AIC_004	The AIC shall periodically provide the CRE with the following information about the VRU detected in its vision area: anonymized unique identifier, position, VRU type and, if possible, direction, speed and behaviour type	AIC (NET)	Communication

PF_UC2-CRE_001	The CRE shall estimate the probability of occurrence of an incident between actors that interact on the road network.	CRE (CE)	Decision
PF_UC2-CRE_002	If the risk of an interaction exceeds a certain value, the CRE shall notify its clients, which in turn shall finally resend them road users	CRE (CE)	Communication
PF_UC2-CVM_001	The Connected Vehicle Manager (CVM) shall be able to receive the CAM and CPM messages sent from the CVs (including the EV), and inform them about events sent from the infrastructure.	CVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-CVM_002	The CVM shall inform the CVs and CAVs about the EVs approaching to their position and provide generic recommendations	CVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-CVM_003	The CVM shall be able to transmit V2X messages to the relevant RSUs for their dissemination to the relevant areas using C-V2X	CVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-CVM_004	The CVM shall be able to disseminate V2X messages based on the location of the Road Users (CVs and CAVs) using 5G technology	CVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-EV_001	The EV shall periodically notify the EVM of the position and speed in its route through the predefined itinerary (if possible, direction should also be included and, also if possible, position should have lane-level accuracy [$<2m$])	EV (CE)	Localization Communication
PF_UC2-EVM_001	The platform shall have an Emergency Vehicle Manager (EVM) able to receive the available corridors from the infrastructure and the updated location of the Emergency Vehicle.	EVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-EVM_002	The EVM shall notify the beginning of a trip of an EV through a predefined itinerary to the TMS	EVM (NET)	Communication

PF_UC2-EVM_003	The EVM shall periodically notify the TMS of the position and speed in its route through its itinerary (if possible, direction should also be included)	EVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-EVM_004	The EVM shall be able to transmit V2X messages to the relevant RSUs for their dissemination to the relevant areas using C-V2X	EVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-EVM_005	The EVM shall be able to disseminate V2X messages based on the location of the Road Users using 5G technology	EVM (NET)	Communication
PF_UC2-TMS_001	The TMS shall process the information of the origins and destinations of the planned trips of connected vehicles to generate an M-OD of planned trips	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_002	Each second, the TMS shall receive the anonymized unique identifier, the georeferenced position, and the speed of each connected vehicle	TMS (NET)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_003	The TMS shall process the position and speed of each CV along time and update the M-OD data model each time a CV begins and ends a trip	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_004	The TMS shall calculate the travel time of each vehicle moving through a link (road segment between two junctions) and record it in the link data model.	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_005	Each traffic control cycle, the TMS shall calculate an average travel time of the vehicles driving along each link (road segment between two junctions) and update the result in the link data model.	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_006	The TMS shall calculate the average travel time for each origin-destination pair (TT-OD) as the average travel time for the path with minimum travel time between the origin and the destination	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_007	The TMS shall calculate the aggregated delay of each entry to each junction per cycle	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion

PF_UC2-TMS_008	Each time a CV enters a junction the TMS shall store a delay record in the junction model associated with the entry and containing the delay of the vehicle	TMS (CE)	Data-fusion
PF_UC2-TMS_009	The TMS shall estimate the arrival time of the EV to each traffic light and take the necessary actions to give traffic light priority to the EVs in their trip across predefined itineraries	TMS (CE)	Decision
PF_UC2-TMS_010	The TMS must inform VRUs and other users of the road network of the current or imminent presence of an EV by activating a Visual Warning Device	TMS (NET)	Movement assist
PF_UC2-VRU_001	CRE must be able to notify vehicles, via the CVM when there is high risk of collision with a VRU	CRE (NET)	Movement assist
PF_UC2-VRU_002	The VRU-APP shall allow a VRU to subscribe to the services of a VRUM	VRU (CE)	Communication
PF_UC2-VRU_003	The VRU-APP shall request the VRU to provide some relevant personal data for the classification of the VRU	VRU (CE)	Data fusion
PF_UC2-VRU_004	AICs must be able to detect the trajectory of previously detected VRUs.	AIC (CE)	Data fusion
PF_UC2-VRU_005	The VRU-APP shall notify VRUM about of the beginning of a trip, the origin and the expected destination of the trip	VRU (CE)	Communication
PF_UC2-VRU_006	The VRUMs shall exchange information with the VRUs they have made a subscription to the services it shall offer.	VRUM (CE)	Communication
PF_UC2-VRU_007	A VRUM shall periodically receive from VRU-APPs information with the identification of each VRU, its position, its direction and its speed.	VRUM (CE)	Communication
PF_UC2-VRU_007	The VRU APP shall notify periodically the position, direction and speed of the VRU to the VRUM	VRU (NET)	Localization
PF_UC2-VRU_008	The VRU-APP shall notify the VRU the detection of a high risk of collision	VRU (CE)	Communication

PF_UC2-VRU_009	The VRUM shall send to the VRUs the high-risk-of-collision alerts that affect them	VRUM (CE)	Actuation
PF_UC2_CAV_001	The CVs shall acquire positioning information from a GNSS device. If possible, with lane-level accuracy (<2m)	CAV	Localization
PF_UC2_CAV_002	The CVs shall send and receive V2X messages to/from the CVM using both communication technologies (5G and C-V2X)	CAV	Communication
PF_UC2_CAV_003	The CVs shall send CAM messages at a 10Hz with the corresponding station type, timestamp and positioning information.	CAV	Communication
PF_UC2_CAV_004	The CVs, if capable, shall generate, encode and send CPM messages at a 10Hz with perception information from its sensors.	CAV	Communication
PF_UC2_CAV_005	The CVs shall be able to receive and decode CAM, CPM, DENM, IVIM and MCM messages.	CAV	Communication
PF_UC2_CAV_006	The CVs shall be able to check the relevance of the received messages depending on its station type, location and dynamics information.	CAV	Decision
PF_UC2_CAV_007	The CVs shall present relevant information from DENMs, IVIMs and MCMs via an HMI in form of a warning/recommendation	CAV	Actuation
PF_UC2_CAV_008	The CVs shall switch between C-V2X and 5G technology based on their location / network availability	CAV	Communication

Figure 1: UC2 - Functional Requirements – Scenarios: SCN1

Figure 2: UC2 - Platform Functional Requirements – Scenarios: SCN2

Figure 3: UC2 - Functional requirements – Scenarios: SCN3

4.2.2. Non-functional Requirements

4.2.2.1. CAVs

This section specifies the requirements that CAV must accomplish to make possible the accomplishment of the functional requirements described in Section 2.1.1, motivated by performance, timing and technology reasons.

Table 9: UC2 – CAV non-functional requirements

ID	Description	Supporting information or docs
P_UC2-CAV_001	GNSS signal must not be lost for more than 50 meters or 5 seconds	Experiences and calculations made by MILLA, and the vehicle ODD reference specifications
P_UC2_CAV_002	RTK service must be configured for every vehicle (to be)	To be compliant with PTCAV_003
P_UC2-CAV_003	GNSS receiver must accept RTK corrections via NTRIP	To be compliant with PTCAV_004
P_UC2-CAV_004	Internet Connection should not disconnect for more than 5 s	To be compliant with PTCAV_004
P_UC2-CAV_005	CAV should send CAM messages at a rate of 10Hz	According to ETSI EN 302 637-2 V1.4.1.
P_UC2-CAV_006	The CVs shall take less than 100ms to generate a CAM message from the corresponding GNSS sample	Applying to short-range (ITS-G5/C-V2X) and 4G/5G V2X devices. The reason is that the CAM generation is 10Hz (max.)
P_UC2-CAV_007	The CVs shall be able to handle between 1 and 10 messages per second to be processed internally	Applying to short-range (ITS-G5/C-V2X) and 4G/5G V2X devices. According to the UC needs, the CV should not need to receive more than 10 messages per second.

4.2.2.2. Networking

This section specifies the requirements that the communications network must accomplish to make possible the accomplishment of the functional requirements described in Section 2.1.2, motivated by performance and timing reasons.

Table 10: UC2 – Non-functional networking requirements

ID	Description	UC type
PNF_UC2-NET_001	Platform should offer 2 s of end-to-end transmission delay for dynamic events, 200 kbps minimum and 99.99% of reliability	RS
PNF_UC2-NET_002	Platform should offer 2 s of end-to-end transmission delay for maneuvers coordination messages, 100 kbps minimum and 99.99% of reliability	CD
PNF_UC2-NET_003	Platform should offer 3 s of end-to-end transmission delay for traffic management messages, 10 kbps minimum and 95% of reliability	TM

4.2.2.3. Computing entities

This section describes the needs in terms of computing entities that are estimated to make possible the accomplishment of the functional requirements described in Section 2.1.3, motivated by performance, timing and technology reasons. Some values are marked “(TBC)” because, at the time or writing the present document, are not yet confirmed and shall be in further stages of the project.

Table 11: UC2 – Number of computing entities

Number of computing entities	Scenario 1 - Emergency vehicle approaching	Scenario 2: Traffic management optimization	Scenario 3 - VRU protection	Physical connections
Cloud	1	1	1	Internet
Edge	6	6	7 (6 shared with UC3, 1 AI camera)	5G, Ethernet, WiFi
Road-side	2	2	2	CV2X Rel 14 Ethernet, WiFi
User	0	0	1	5G
Vehicle	7 (TBC)	7	7 (TBC)	CV2X, 5G

4.3. UC3 – Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled traffic management in the Mediterranean cross-border corridor

4.3.1. Functional requirements

Table 12 UC3 - Functional Requirements – Functionality

Subsystem/entity	Functions (optional info: subfunctions included)
CV & CAV	
CV – Connected vehicles (including CAVs) via OBUs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Localization (positioning and map-matching) Human Machine Interaction (Warning, recommendation) Communication (encoding/decoding, transmission/reception, network)
CAVs – Connected autonomous vehicles (e.g. MILLA autonomous shuttle)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception (sensing, V2X-based, data fusion) Localization (positioning and map-matching) Decision (Autonomous Driving level, threat assessment) Human Machine Interaction (HMI) (warning, recommendation) Actuation (simulated via HMI) Communication (encoding/decoding, transmission/reception, network)
RSU – Road Side Units	
5G antennas	Transmission/reception of data between vehicles/road users and the infrastructure
C-V2X antennas	Transmission/reception of data between vehicles/road users and the infrastructure
Traffic cameras (roadside video sensors)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception Transmission of video feed
MEC (Edge)	
Local TMC (Traffic Management Center) including LDM (Local Dynamic Map)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data fusion Incident detection Incident notification generation (alert, info message) Local traffic state perception Local traffic strategy generator (edge, low latency) LDM: dynamically updated database of vehicles on each road section
Mobility Hub Edge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring /registry of vehicles Communication with CVs via V2X gateways (message generation, transmission, reception) Communication with the Mobility Hub Cloud Enables running apps on top of it (TMC, video analytics, etc.)
Video Analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Processing in real-time the traffic camera feed Detection of any stopped vehicles (incidents)

	Calculation of traffic intensity
VRU Safety Risk Detector	VRU threat assessment (e.g. collision with approaching vehicle)
Vehicle Awareness Dissemination	Dissemination of basic awareness information stored in the LDM among CVs using different radio technologies
V2X Gateways	Management and control of transmission/reception of V2X messages between CVs/VRUs and infrastructure using two different radio technologies (5G and/or C-V2X).
CLOUD	
TMC Global	Fusion of local traffic states into global traffic state perception Global traffic strategy generator (manoeuvre support, e.g. speed, distance, lane, etc.)
Mobility Hub Cloud	Enables running apps on top of it Communication with Mobility Hub Edge(s) Data Storage, e.g. global perception states
Tele-supervision center for the MILLA shuttle	Monitor MILLA shuttle (CAV) status and location via HMI Communication with the shuttle (manoeuvre message generation) Communication with the Mobility Hub and TMC
VRU (mobile)	
Shuttle passengers (mobile app-1)	Shuttle user registration Shuttle “booking” Communication (message generation, transmission/reception) Information (e.g. shuttle travel information)
VRUs (Vulnerable Road Users, via mobile app-2)	Register of VRUs Localization (positioning) Movement assist (threat assessment) Communication (ITS message generation/transmission/reception)

Table 13 UC3- Functional Requirements – both scenarios

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
CV & CAV			
PF_UC3-CAV_001	The use case will take place with max 2 CAVs (MILLA and IDIADA) and at least 2 additional connected conventional vehicles	CAV	-

PF_UC3-CAV_002	The CAVs (MILLA and IDIADA) shall have frontal sensors to perceive other vehicles and VRUs	CAV	Perception (sensing)
PF_UC3-CAV_003	The CAVs shall be aware of road events through DENM ITS messages	CAV	Perception (V2X-based)
PF_UC3-CAV_004	The MILLA shuttle CAV will be capable of autonomously driving on the highway at SAE 4, at an appropriate speed for driving on the highway in real traffic [OPTIONAL] The same for IDIADA CAV	CAV	Decision
PF_UC3-CAV_005	The MILLA CAV shuttle shall respond to the speed/maneuver recommendations sent by the infrastructure automatically [OPTIONAL] The same for IDIADA CAV	CAV	Decision
PF_UC3-CAV_007	The CAVs and CVs shall have 5G and C-V2X connectivity simultaneously (via an OBU and an on-board 5G modem)	CAV	Communication
PF_UC3-CAV_008	The CAVs and CVs shall have a GNSS with lane-level accuracy (if possible)	CAV	Localization (positioning)
PF_UC3-CAV_009	The OBUs/TCUs of all CAVs and CVs shall be able to transmit and receive messages to/from the Gateway in the formats selected, including CAM, CPM, MCM, DENM, IVIM and Raw ITS messages	CAV, RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-CAV_010	The IDIADA CAV shall have a processing unit able to interact between the TCU, the HMI and the internal vehicle systems	CAV	Human Machine Interaction Decision
PF_UC3-CAV_011	The IDIADA CAV and each conventional CV will have an HMI device (e.g. tablet) to show traffic/maneuver recommendations to the drivers	CAV	Human Machine Interaction Actuation
PF_UC3-CAV_012	The MILLA shuttle CAV will communicate with the "Remote	CAV, CLOUD	Monitor CAV Communication

	Shuttle Supervision Service" (human) and shall be remotely monitored and controlled by it		
PF_UC3-CAV_013	The infrastructure should integrate a connectivity strategy to guarantee that CAVs Fleet-Manager has a perception of the vehicle under the scope of the infrastructure (e.g. transmit geolocation of the CAV from infrastructure to Fleet Manager)	CLOUD	Communication Monitor location
PF_UC3-CAV_014	In case of incident involving the CAV (Shuttle), the infrastructure will inform to the service owner about it	CAV, MEC, CLOUD	Communication Monitor status
PF_UC3-CAV_015	The infrastructure (e.g. cloud) should enable a secondary communication channel via C-V2X between the MILLA Cloud fleet managers and the MILLA CAV, in case of loss of 5G communication	RSU	Communication
RSU – Road Side Units			
PF_UC3-RSU_001	5G network shall be offered at an available private or public frequency band. 5G Network shall cover the whole demo area, both directions, all lanes and including singular spots (i.e. service area, rest zones...)	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-RSU_002	The infrastructure shall offer 4G connectivity at the service pickup/drop-off points, for the CAVs to connect to service-oriented applications	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-RSU_003	In the Spanish section of the highway, at least 4 RSUs with C-V2X will be installed, with sufficient connectivity coverage for both directions and all the lanes and singular spots	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-RSU_004	The highway shall feature at least 5 FullHD or 4K cameras, connected	RSU	Perception

	and feeding real-time video footage to the local MEC (Hub Edge)		Transmission of video feed
MEC (Edge)			
PF_UC3-MEC_001	The highway shall be equipped with at least 2 MECs in the Spanish side and at least 1 MEC in the French side (i.e. side of the border)	MEC	
PF_UC3-MEC_002	The MEC shall have a Mobility Hub Edge Platform module, over which is possible to deploy specific software components, incl. Video Analytics (VA), Local TMC, and Digital Twin (DT)	MEC	Enables running apps on top of it
PF_UC3-MEC_003	The Mobility Hub Edge Platform shall receive all data coming from local infrastructure, vehicles and devices (via Gateways) and distribute them to the respective MEC software modules	MEC	Communication with CVs via V2X
PF_UC3-MEC_004	The Mobility Hub Edge Platform shall transmit data, including traffic management information or traffic instructions to the vehicles in its local area (via Gateways)	MEC, RSU	Communication with CVs via V2X gateways
PF_UC3-MEC_005	The MEC shall have a Video Analytics (VA) module which will run on top of the Mobility Hub Edge and shall receive real-time video feed, process it, and transmit the traffic perception info to the DT and Local TMC	MEC, RSU	Processing real-time traffic feed Incident detection
PF_UC3-MEC_006	The VA shall be able to detect vehicles (moving or static), recognise their type/category, and capture their location, speed, trajectory	MEC	Processing real-time traffic feed
PF_UC3-MEC_007	The MEC shall have a Digital Twin (DT) module which will run on top of the Mobility Hub Edge	MEC	Enables running apps on top of it
PF_UC3-MEC_008	The Digital Twin (DT) shall have a Local Dynamic Map (LDM) that is updated using the data (e.g.	MEC	Local traffic state perception LDM

	geolocation, speed) transmitted by vehicles and VRUs		
PF_UC3-MEC_009	The LDM shall contain static road attributes	MEC	LDM
PF_UC3-MEC_010	The LDM shall provide as output the future expected trajectories of each road actor (vehicles and pedestrians) in the short term	MEC	Local traffic state perception LDM
PF_UC3-MEC_011	The DT shall calculate and store a local traffic status periodically, using as input the fusion of data sources (camera data, LDM data, obstacle/incident data)	MEC	Data fusion Local traffic state perception
PF_UC3-MEC_012	The local traffic status shall be periodically transmitted from the MEC to the Cloud	MEC	Communication with the Mobility Hub Cloud
PF_UC3-MEC_013	The MEC shall have a Local Traffic Management Center (TMC) module which will run on top of the Mobility Hub Edge	MEC	Enables running apps on top of it
PF_UC3-MEC_014	Periodically the TMC shall calculate an average travel time of the vehicles driving along each highway section and store the result	MEC	Local traffic state perception
PF_UC3-MEC_015	The Local TMC will identify and register local incidents and create a notification/alert to be communicated to the relevant vehicles	MEC, CAV	Incident notification generation (alert, info message)
PF_UC3-MEC_016	The Local TMC shall calculate the local traffic management strategies, for low-latency	MEC	Local traffic state perception
PF_UC3-MEC_017	The traffic management strategy messages transmitted by the infrastructure to the vehicles shall be related to a) modify max speed, b) modify distance from car in-front, c) closed/open lane (to be avoided / preferred)	MEC, CAV	Local traffic strategy generator Communication with CVs

PF_UC3-MEC_018	The V2X Gateways shall enable to transmit Facilities messages over IPv4 over cellular networks	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-MEC_019	The Gateways shall enable to transmit Facilities messages over LTE-PC5 radio technology	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-MEC_020	The Gateways shall translate messages between different radio technologies	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-MEC_021	Both Gateways shall have the same interfaces to communicate with the Hub Edge	RSU, MEC	Communication
PF_UC3-MEC_022	The Gateways shall feed the Hub Edge with the incoming messages from the vehicles and VRUs	RSU, MEC	Communication
PF_UC3-MEC_023	The Gateways shall allow the infrastructure (via Hub Edge) to send information to the road users (CAM, CPM, MCM, DENM, IVIM)	RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-MEC_024	The i2CAT Gateway shall optimize the Cooperative Awareness (CA) information transmitted to road users by aggregating CA information into CPM messages	RSU	Communication
CLOUD			
PF_UC3-CLOUD_001	The Mobility Hub Cloud Platform shall transmit and receive data to/from the Hub Edge Platform(s)	MEC, CLOUD	Communication with Mobility Hub Edge(s)
PF_UC3-CLOUD_002	The Mobility Hub Cloud Platform shall contain a data repository, a data management module and data gateway, and interconnects with the Global TMC and other components such as the Shuttle Supervision Service	CLOUD	Data storage Enables running apps on top of it
PF_UC3-CLOUD_003	The Global TMC will construct the macroscopic global perception of traffic for multiple sections of the highway	CLOUD	Fusion of local traffic states into global traffic state perception

PF_UC3-CLOUD_004	The Global TMC will simulate and select the best global traffic management strategies	CLOUD	Global traffic strategy generator
PF_UC3-CLOUD_005	The MILLA Remote Shuttle Supervision Service shall monitor the location and status of the MILLA CAV (displayed via a web HMI)	CLOUD	Monitor status & location
PF_UC3-CLOUD_006	The Remote Shuttle Supervision Service shall communicate driving/manoeuvre directions to the CAV, as well as new route destination	CLOUD	Communication with the shuttle
PF_UC3-CLOUD_007	The Remote Shuttle Supervision Service shall intercommunicate with the (Global) Mobility Hub and TMC	CLOUD	Communication with the Mobility Hub & TMC
VRU (mobile)			
PF_UC3-VRU_001	The VRUs and the MILLA shuttle passengers shall have an Android mobile phone application, connected to the internet via 4G or 5G, and feature a GPS sensor Communication is done via TCP/IPv4 and cellular networks	VRU	User Registry Registration
PF_UC3-VRU_002	The VRUs app shall transmit VAM messages with their position, speed and direction at a frequency high enough to detect dangerous situations	VRU, RSU	Localization Communication
PF_UC3-VRU_003	VRUs app shall receive CAMs, DENMs and CPMs from the infrastructure, at a frequency high enough to detect dangerous situations	VRU, RSU	Communication
PF_UC3-VRU_004	The VRU app shall trigger an alarm when a vehicle (e.g. MILLA CAV) detected by PODIUM system is too close to the VRU and represents a threat for her/his safety	VRU	User Registry Localization Threat assessment
PF_UC3-VRU_005	The MILLA shuttle passenger App shall allow users (passengers) to register	VRU	User Registration

PF_UC3-VRU_006	The MILLA shuttle passenger App shall have a Fast check-in system to directly access the shuttle at the shuttle stop, without pre-reservation	VRU	Shuttle “booking”
PF_UC3-VRU_007	The Passenger App shall be able to receive relevant shuttle trip information from the infrastructure (e.g. shuttle location, next time of departure, time of arrival at destination)	VRU	Communication Information
PF_UC3-VRU_008	The Passenger App shall display travel related information to the user	VRU	Information
PF_UC3-VRU_009	The Passenger App shall have a modality to allow users to send light packets (unattended) from point to point using the MILLA shuttle (logistics)	VRU	Shuttle “booking”

The main interactions between the different functional entities for each scenario are depicted below.

Figure 4 UC3 - Functional requirements – Scenario: SCN1

Figure 5 UC3 - Functional Requirements – Scenario: SCN2

4.3.2. Non-functional requirements

4.3.2.1. CAVs

The non-functional requirements for the CAV of MILLA (001-004) and the CVs (005-006).

Table 14 UC3 – CAV and CV requirements

ID	Description	Supporting information or docs
P_UC3-CAV_001	GNSS signal must not be lost for more than 50 meters or 5 seconds	-
P_UC3_CAV_002	RTK service must be configured for every vehicle (to be)	To be compliant with PTCAV_003
P_UC3-CAV_003	GNSS receiver must accept RTK corrections via NTRIP	To be compliant with PTCAV_004
P_UC3-CAV_004	Internet Connection should not disconnect for more than 5 seconds	To be compliant with PTCAV_004
P_UC3-CAV_005	The CVs shall take less than 100ms to generate a CAM message from the corresponding GNSS sample	Applying to short-range (ITS-G5/C-V2X) and 4G/5G V2X devices The reason is that the CAM generation is 10Hz (max.)

P_UC3-CAV_006	The CVs shall be able to handle > 10 messages per second to be processed internally	Applying to 4G/5G V2X communication
---------------	---	-------------------------------------

4.3.2.2. Networking

For the correct functioning of the UC3 system, the following non-functional requirements are set, covering networking, traffic camera feed transmission, MEC-Cloud connection, low-latency incident alert transmission, and Tele-supervision.

Table 15 UC3 – networking requirements

ID	Description	UC type
P_UC3-NET_001	Networking latency (CAM, CPM, etc.) of < 1 seconds, Throughput 1-5 Mbps, and Reliability > 95%	TM
P_UC3-NET_002	Traffic Camera feed (via 5G): latency < 100 ms, Throughput 1 Mbps (for HD, 15fps), and Reliability > 95%	TM
P_UC3-NET_003	Low-latency Incident alert (e.g. DENM): transmission latency (from PDI to CVs) < 1 s, Throughput 10-100 kbps, Reliability > 99%	RS
P_UC3-NET_004	Tele-supervision function: Latency < 100 ms, Throughput 2-5 Mbps, and Reliability > 90%	RS
P_UC3-NET_005	MEC-CLOUD Connection latency of <1 seconds, Throughput 1-5 Mbps, and Reliability > 95%	TM

4.3.2.3. Computing entities

The UC will be cross-border in the AP7 highway that connects Spain with France. One independent Cloud (Mobility Hub & Global TMC) will be setup in each side of the border. The Spanish cloud will coordinate 2 MECs, while the French cloud only 1 MEC. Traffic cameras will only be available on the Spanish side. Therefore, the Spanish MECs will need to have GPU capacity for processing the real-time video feed.

5G network coverage will need to be ubiquitous along the highway, in both border sides. In “hotspots” (tentatively: on the border crossing, in front of Gran Junquera commercial center where there are highway entries/exits, etc.), additional C-V2X coverage will be implemented with RSUs.

Each CAV and CV will be equipped with C-V2X OBUs, an on-board laptop with 5G modem, and a lane-accuracy GNSS. Shuttle passengers and VRUs will have an Android mobile phone with the respective PODIUM apps installed.

Table 16 UC3 – number of computing entities

Computing entities	Number (both scenarios)	Physical connections
Cloud	2 Clouds (1 in Spain, 1 in France)	None (Internet access only)
Edge	3 MECs (2 in Spain including GPU, 1 in France)	SFP+ 1 GbE 10 GbE WiFi

Road side	At least 4 C-V2X – RSUs	C-V2X GNSS
User (mobile phone)	4 max (shuttle passengers and VRU pedestrians)	Minimum 4G, if possible 5G with compatible frequency (FR1 + FR2) GPS enabled (with precise location)
Vehicle (incl. OBUs)	4-5 vehicles in total = 1-2 CAVs + 3-4 CVs	Ethernet LTE-PC5 5G Modem / 4G WiFi USB CAN-Bus GNSS

4.4. UC4 – Trusted cooperative perception for intersection manoeuvre assistance

4.4.1. Functional requirements

The Intersection Manoeuvres Assistance takes mainly information from optical sensors and CCAM messages to replicate digitally a crossing point where VRUs are present. A CAV will have to cross the crossing point according to indications provided by the PDI. The interactions between the identified computing entities and the necessary functionalities to fulfil this task continuously, are described as functional requirements. Since the timing is critical, involving continuous movement of the potentially contending users, the performance of UC4 depends on the requirements described in the following section of non-functional requirements.

Table 17: UC4 – Functional Requirements – Functionality

Subsystem/entity	Functions (optional info: subfunctions included)
CAV	Perception (sensing, V2X-based p., data fusion) Localization (positioning and map-matching) Decision (AD level, threat assessment) Human Machine Interaction (Warning, recommendation, ODD inform) Actuation (simulated via HMI) Communication (encoding/decoding, dispatching/receive, network)
RSU	Attestation Perception Communication
MEC	Attestation Data fusion (digital twin, truth assessment) Movement assist (threat assessment, manoeuver Support) Communication (message generation, dispatching)

Table 18: UC4 – Functional Requirements – Scenarios: Give way, stop and wait, passthrough, prevented start, collision avoidance

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
PF_UC4-CAV_001	CAV shall have frontal sensors to perceive VRU and other vehicles	CAV	Perception (sensing)
PF_UC4-CAV_002	CAV shall be able to receive V2X DENM messages about road events	CAV	Perception (V2X-based)
PF_UC4-CAV_003	CAV shall use GNSS and RTK corrections to localize	CAV	Localization (positioning)

PF_UC4-CAV_004	CAV shall match on the local intersection map, received from the MAPEM	CAV	Localization (map-matching)
PF_UC4-CAV_005	CAV shall implement an AMQP client to exchange messages with MEC	CAV	Communication (dispatching)
PF_UC4-CAV_006	CAV shall include an OBU for C-V2X direct communication (PC5) to exchange messages with RSU	CAV	Communication (dispatching)
PF_UC4-CAV_007	CAV shall send/receive message with geo-networking header, security header and message payload over AMQP	CAV	Communication (encoding/decoding)
PF_UC4-CAV_008...	CAV shall encode and send perceived objects via CPM	CAV	Communication (encoding/decoding)
PF_UC4-CAV_009	CAV shall receive IVI, SPAT, MAP, DENM messages	CAV	Communication (encoding/decoding)
PF_UC4-CAV_010	CAV shall have 5G network connectivity to a MEC	CAV	Communication (networking)
PF_UC4-CAV_011	CAV shall use time-to-pass information from IVI messages to evaluate next manoeuvres	CAV	Decision
PF_UC4-CAV_012	CAV shall evaluate AD level based on perceived objects and road events	CAV	Decision
PF_UC4-CAV_013	CAV shall give advice to the driver on when to pass the intersection	CAV	HMI (recommendation)
PF_UC4-CAV_014	CAV shall inform the driver about the allowed level of automation (current and future)	CAV	HMI (ODD inform)
PF_UC4-NET_001	RSU shall be connected physically with a camera sensor and LIDAR via ethernet. RSU is also connected to the MEC server via 5G.	NET	Perception, Communication
PF_UC4-CE_001	The Camera/LIDAR sensors shall point to the crossing point with pedestrian crossings.	CE	Perception
PF_UC4-CE_002	The RSU perceives and tracks pedestrians and other road users	CE	Perception, Communication,

	and transmits perceptions to the Digital Twin service running on the MEC server.		
PF_UC4-CAV_015	CAVs shall communicate their sensor information (CPM, CAM messages) to the MEC server using hybrid CV2X (via RSU) and 5G.	CAV	Communication
PF_UC4-CE_003	VRUs can communicate to the MEC server their position and planned path through a smartphone.	CE	Communication
PF_UC4-CE_004	The Digital twin keeps updated the status of the cross point with the sensor and road user’s dynamic information via CCAM messages.	CE	Data fusion
PF_UC4-CE_005	The truthfulness module subscribes to the Digital Twin and calculates truth indexes on the information in the digital twin.	CE	Data fusion
PF_UC4-CE_006	The VIMA service shall subscribe to the Digital Twin to produce IVIM indications for CAV.	CE	Movement assist

Figure 6: UC4 - Functional Requirements – Scenarios: Give way, stop and wait, passthrough, prevented start, collision avoidance

In the attestation scenario, every trusted node is challenged to be trustworthy by means of periodic verification with the attestation entities present in the PDI, so the nodes can be authorized to provide information to the PDI used for the current use case 4.

Table 19: UC4 – Functional Requirements – Scenario: Attestation

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
PF_UC4-SEC_002	MEC server and RSU act as attestation entities of the attestation protocol.	CE	Attestation
PF_UC4-SEC_003	Attestation Entities allow the attestation of the trustworthiness of the OBUs and RSUs present in the system.	CE	Attestation
PF_UC4-SEC_004	Attestation entities might block a RSU or OBU from transmitting data to the PDI.	CE,NET	Attestation, communication
PF_UC4-SEC_005	Attestation entities communicate periodically with OBUs and RSUs for trustworthiness.	CE,NET	communication

Figure 7: UC4 - Platform Functional Requirements – Scenario: Attestation

4.4.2. Non-functional Requirements

4.4.2.1. CAVs

UC4 VIMA supports ADAS and Automated Driving in urban scenario, with focus on VRU protection. Collective perception data are fused on the digital twin at MEC and then used by VIMA application to generate a recommendation. The message received by the CAV influences the crossing manoeuvre, potentially a fully automated one. The received (in particular from IVIM, DENM, MAPEM, SPATEM) as

well as the transmitted information (on CAM and CPM) must be timely and accurate, and the capability of the vehicle to position itself on the intersection must meet strict performance requirements. The non-functional requirements relate indeed to the accuracy of the information which is provided in CCAM messages; to the high precision of positioning and to the age of information from the time it is received to the time it is presented to the driver and/or used for actuation.

Table 20: UC4 – CAV non-functional requirements

ID	Description	Supporting information or docs
PNF_UC4-CAV_001	The CAV shall generate/receive reliable CCAM messages (false positive/negative <1%, <10% tolerated for Living Lab proof-of-concept)	Experience in R&D procedures.
PNF_UC4-CAV_002	Positioning accuracy shall be <1.5 m, and < 0.2m with RTK correction	5G-CARMEN D5.3 final pilot report
PNF_UC4-CAV_003	The latency introduced by information processing (from message reception to actuation/warning should not exceed 100ms.	Estimation of T6-T3 with ref. to ETSI TS 101 539-3 V1.1.1 (2013-11) Longitudinal Collision Risk Warning (LCRW) application requirements specification

4.4.2.2. Networking

Since the VRU-Aware Intersection movement assistance is based on dynamic events triggered by road events in a reduced space, being the nature of the events asynchronous, the communication platform should support the Road Safety use case category for dynamic events.

In UC4 also the communication platform should support Cooperative Driving Use Case Category for processed data (since CPM and CAMs are the processed data), which is updating the PDI with the cross point status.

Table 21: UC4 Networking Requirements

ID	Description	UC type
PNF_UC4-NET_001	Platform should offer 40 ms of OW delay, 20-30 kbps minimum for dynamic data and 99.99% of reliability	RS
PNF_UC4-NET_002	Platform should offer 40 ms of OW delay, 4 Mbps minimum and 99.9% of reliability to support UC4.	CD

4.4.2.3. Computing Entities

The UC4 identifies 4 types of computing entities, given the latencies involved into the application, no cloud will be used, but an edge node with processing capabilities to host the digital twin and the VIMA service that reads and process vehicle movement indications; it also hosts attestation and truthfulness modules. One RSU for one intersection, equipped with camera sensors and GPU processing capabilities to perceive road users. The VRUs are pedestrians with an appropriate App and finally vehicles (one is only necessary) are equipped with on-board-units.

Table 22: UC4 – number of computing entities

Number of computing entities	All Scenarios	Physical connections
Cloud	0	
Edge	1	Network connection to the 5G RAN
Road-side	1	CV2X, 5G, LTE, WiFi
User	1	VRU App
Vehicle	1 or 2 (one CAV, one CV TBD)	CV2X/G5, 5G, LTE, ethernet

4.5. UC5 – Risk management in a highway tunnel

4.5.1. Functional requirements

The objective of UC5 is to demonstrate how risk management within a Tunnel can be effective, by means of: (1) an improved awareness of the situation by the infrastructure (also by means of the digital twin), (2) full coverage of C-ITS infrastructure before, within and after the tunnel, (3) GNSS coverage for the CAV also within the tunnel thus extending the current V2X in support of ADAS and automated driving functions on highway, most prominently C-ACC, lane change recommendations and hazard warning for disengagement. Functional requirements of UC5 are related to the specific components detecting the risk, the digital twin representation of the current situation, the C-ITS V2I warning services (and the interaction with road operator), the GNSS capabilities within the tunnel, the V2X functionalities as well as the enabled assistance/automated functions within the vehicle.

Table 23: UC5 – Functionality Table

Subsystem/entity	Functions (optional info: subfunctions included)
CAV	Perception (sensing, V2X-based p., data fusion) Localization (positioning indoor and outdoor) Decision (AD level) Human Machine Interaction (Warning, ODD inform) Actuation (Longitudinal; lateral simulated via HMI) Communication (encoding/decoding, dispatching/receive, network)
RSU	Perception Communication
CLOUD	Data fusion (digital twin, truth assessment) Risk assessment Communication (message generation, dispatching)

Table 24: UC5 – Functional requirements – All scenarios

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
PF_UC5-CAV_001	CAV shall have frontal sensors to perceive other vehicles	CAV	Perception (sensing)

PF_UC5-CAV_002	CAV shall be aware of road events through V2X DENM	CAV	Perception (V2X-based)
PF_UC5-CAV_003	CAV shall be aware of road signs (speed limit and other signage) through V2X IVI	CAV	Perception (V2X-based)
PF_UC5-CAV_004	CAV shall use V2V, V2I and sensor data in combination, for understanding the scene and AD ODD	CAV	Perception
PF_UC5-CAV_005	CAV shall use GNSS signal and RTK corrections to localize outside the tunnel	CAV	Localization (positioning)
PF_UC5-CAV_006	CAV shall use the indoor positioning solutions to localize inside the tunnel	CAV	Localization (positioning)
PF_UC5-CAV_007	CAV shall use the indoor positioning solutions as time reference for the V2X short range communication	CAV	Communication (time referencing)
PF_UC5-CAV_008	CAV shall implement an AMQP client to receive message from cloud	CAV	Communication (dispatching)
PF_UC5-CAV_009	CAV shall include an OBU for C-V2X direct communication (PC5) to exchange messages with RSU	CAV	Communication (dispatching)
PF_UC5-CAV_010	CAV shall receive messages with geo-networking header, security header and message payload over AMQP	CAV	Communication (encoding/decoding)
PF_UC5-CAV_011	CAV shall receive IVI and DENM messages	CAV	Communication (encoding/decoding)
PF_UC5-CAV_012	CAV shall have at 4G network connectivity to cloud service	CAV	Communication (networking)
PF_UC5-CAV_013	CAV shall use V2V and V2I information to evaluate next manoeuvres	CAV	Decision
PF_UC5-CAV_014	CAV shall evaluate AD level based on perceived objects and road events	CAV	Decision

PF_UC5-CAV_015	CAV shall utilize sensor and V2X information for cruise control	CAV	Actuation (longitudinal control)
PF_UC5-CAV_016	CAV shall be capable of L3 Highway Chauffeur (although not de facto actuated on public roads, it shall be “available” for engagement)	CAV	Automated Driving function
PF_UC5-CAV_017	CAV shall utilize sensor and V2X information for lane change recommendations	CAV	HMI (recommendation)
PF_UC5-CAV_018	CAV shall inform the driver about hazard warning	CAV	HMI (hazard warning)
PF_UC5-CAV_019	CAV shall inform the driver about the allowed level of automation (current and future)	CAV	HMI (ODD inform)
PF_UC5_CE_001	RSUs with camera sensor perceive vehicles coming in and out the tunnel and characterize their type.	CE	Perception
PF_UC5_NET_001	RSUs send the perceived vehicle perceptions and vehicle counts and send them to the cloud digital twin using 4G.	NET	communication
PF_UC5_CE_002	The cloud RMT calculates the risk level status from Digital Twin	CE	Risk assessment
PF_UC5_CE_003	The cloud Risk Level Assessment Publisher publishes notifications to vehicles via AMQP	CE	Communications Risk Assessment
PF_UC5_NET_002	Tunnel infrastructure will recreate GNSS signals inside the tunnel to support CAV localization	NET	Positioning
PF_UC5_NET_003	CAV will use also ITS-G5 received signals from RSUs (trilateration) to localize inside the tunnel	NET	Positioning

Figure 8: UC2 - Platform functional requirements – Scenario: Risk maintenance

4.5.2. Non-functional requirements

4.5.2.1. CAVs

In UC 5 a vehicle with Highway Chauffeur capabilities is facing the entrance of a tunnel. The CAV must be aware in advance of possible hazards and risks impacting on ODD exit conditions. It must be capable of receiving assistance by the road infrastructure, in order to keep the cooperative functions (e.g. C-ACC) operational in ordinary conditions, or to disengage assisted/automated driving functions in case of risk. Non-functional requirements at CAV in UC5 are related to the advance of information, to the continuity (minimizing gaps) of self-positioning and to its performance at least at lane-level (to correctly interpret the V2V and V2I received info).

Table 25: UC5 – Non-functional CAV requirements

ID	Description	Supporting information or docs
PNF_UC5-CAV_001	ODD exit indication should be given according to the SAE Level of automation.	Derived from SAE J3016 definitions. L4 will not be tested, but the advance of information will be evaluated
PNF_UC5_CAV_002	Imminent hazard condition detection should be performed with a maximum reaction time < 100 ms at CAV (message reception to actuation)	Estimation of T6-T3 with ref. to ETSI TS 101 539-3 V1.1.1 (2013-11) Longitudinal Collision Risk Warning (LCRW) application requirements specification
PNF_UC5-CAV_003	Positioning accuracy inside the tunnel shall meet at least 1.5 m	Lane-level position requirement, considering 3.0-4.0 m lanes

PNF_UC5-CAV_004	The CAV shall be capable of having a continuous position and timing reference when entering/exiting a tunnel, with tolerated outage of 100 ms (maximum value).	No C-ITS message should be lost due to positioning outage. CAM maximum frequency yields the upper bound of 100ms tolerance.
-----------------	--	---

4.5.2.2. Networking

The Use case requires from the platform the physical capabilities to support Use Case Categories Cooperative Driving and Traffic Management, since the CAV can activate the cooperative ACC while in the tunnel, so sharing sensor information; on the other hand, the resulting notification might lead to a routing decision or ODD exit, which is a much slower process.

In this use case, one of the PDI’s services is the signal provision of the GNSS inside the tunnel. A requirement is needed since the entire tunnel must be covered by the signal.

Table 26: UC5 – Non-functional Network requirements

ID	Description	UC type
P_UC5-NET_001	Platform should offer 40 ms of OW delay, 4 Mbps minimum and 99.9% of reliability to support UC4, in accordance to UC category cooperative Driving with sensor sharing of processed data.	CD
P_UC5-NET_002	Platform should guarantee an OW delay in the order 1 s, 10 kbps and 95% of reliability, in accordance to UC Category Traffic management	TM
P_UC5-NET_003	The system for indoor GNSS signal provision shall cover the entire length of the tunnel with an appropriate signal equivalent to the signal level outside.	-

4.5.2.3. Computing entities

The Use Case requires that the platform provides at least a computing entity to hold Digital Twin and Tunnel Risk Management Services. Other entities are Road Side Units with sensors connected via ethernet interfaces. RSUs must be able to communicate with vehicles and with the cloud via LTE-A.

Since this is a highway Use Case, no users or VRU companion devices are required.

At least one CAV is required to support the use case and at least one connected vehicle, sharing information for cooperative ACC. Vehicles are required to have hybrid communication for redundancy.

Table 27: UC5 – number of computing entities

Number of computing entities	All scenarios	Physical connections
Cloud	1	Connected near the TIM Cloud
Edge	0	
Road-side	2	LTE-A, CV2X/G5, WiFi, eth
User	0	
Vehicle	2 min. 1 CAV, 1 or more CV	CAV: LTE, CV2X, CAN CV: LTE, CV2X/G5, eth, WiFi

5. Platform requirements

Along with all the functionality and performance-linked requirements identified for each UC, the most identified transversal requirements were related to networking and computing entities. Besides, CCAM messages requirements are also described, as common requirements and use-case-specific requirements. Finally, we provide a list of the trust and security related identified requirements.

5.1. Functional Common Platform Requirements

Table 28: Platform Functional Requirements

ID	Description	Component(s)	Functionality
PF_NET_001	CCAM communicating entities shall send/receive message with geo-networking header, security header and message payload over a publish-subscribe protocol to communicate via cellular communication	NET	Communication (encoding/decoding)
PNF_NET_002	CAVs and road users shall support cellular (5G/4G) communication with the MEC/Cloud entities	NET	From D2.1
PNF_NET_003	Road users shall use short range (G5 / CV2X) communication to interact with RSUs or other road users	NET	From D2.1
PNF_CE_001	An HMI shall communicate AD actuations (when present) and notifications to the driver on all connected vehicles.	CE	From D2.1
PNF_CE_002	Connected VRUs shall send VAM messages to update MEC/cloud entities about their status	CE	From D2.1
PNF_CE_003	Interactions between road users and RSU/Edge/Cloud entities shall use CCAM messages	CE	From D2.1
PNF_CAV_001	CAVs shall be able to send their positions via CAM messages to MEC/cloud	CAV	from use cases
PNF_CAV_002	The CAVs shall be able to react on received CCAM messages accordingly, limited to use case needs	CAV	from use cases

PNF_CE_004	Camera sensors are used for road user detection	CE	from use cases
PNF_CAV_003	The CAVs and CVs shall be able to check the relevance of the received messages in order to consume them and actuate accordingly.	CAV	from use cases
PNF_CE_004	Digital Twins are present in MEC/Cloud components	CE	from use cases
PNF_CE_005	The MEC/Cloud platform entities shall analyze the road situation and UC objectives, and respond accordingly with actions to be accomplished by road users.	CE	from use cases

5.2. Non-functional common platform requirements

5.2.1. CAVs

Table 29: Non-functional CAV Platform requirements

ID	Description	Motivation
P_CAV_001	The V2X system on CAV shall have state-of-art performance: at physical layer, 300m range in PC5/ITS-G5 (ref. PDR>90%).	V2X performance is a pre-requisite in order to use V2X as sensor for Connected and Automated Driving.
P_CAV_002	At facility layer: decode at least 1000msg/s with SEC payload.	V2X performance is a pre-requisite in order to use V2X as sensor for Connected and Automated Driving.
P_CAV_003	At application layer: handle at least 10 relevant messages/s.	V2X performance is a pre-requisite in order to use V2X as sensor for Connected and Automated Driving.
P_CAV_004	Data latency across layers (Tx/Rx) < 100ms overall.	V2X performance is a pre-requisite in order to use V2X as sensor for Connected and Automated Driving.
P_CAV_005	The self-positioning capability of CAV shall comply with the AD task needs on the different scenarios, at minimum: 1.5 m for lane-level ego-positioning; sub-meter accuracy (< 0.5m) for collective perception.	The CAV needs to correctly filter for relevance the warning received by the infrastructure, and transmit its own lane-level defined position in CAM. When sending sensed objects (CPM), taking error propagation into

P_CAV_006	CAV shall have an HMI to interact with the driver	account, sub-meter accuracy is recommended. From D2.1 high level requirements
P_CAV_007	All CAVs shall localize with at least lane-level accuracy	From D2.1 high level requirements

5.2.2. Networking

Networking non-functional platform requirements have been identified by identifying their use case types associated. Every UC have latency, associated bandwidth and packet reliability which can fit into each UC conditions. It can be said that platform supports the use case types requirements associated with their types, as in Table 30.(see also annex).

Table 30: Non-functional networking platform requirements

ID	Description	Motivation
P_NET_001	Platform supports Cooperative Driving Use case type	UC1, UC4
P_NET_002	Platform supports Road Safety use case type	UC1, UC2, UC3, UC4
P_NET_003	Platform supports Traffic Management use case type	UC2, UC3, UC5

5.2.3. Computing entities

Time synchronization is another low-level requirement which allows the proper functionality of the Use Cases; it gives absolute information between events detected, to know at any time the age of a given event information, crucial for movement prediction or accurate process timing measurements. It is also useful for performance measurements such as the transport or application delay and availability time.

Table 31: Non-functional Computing Entities platform requirements

ID	Description	Motivation
P_CE_001	Time synchronization between computing entities must allow a maximum of 1ms	This is due to the need to measure timestamps to evaluate performance latencies in milliseconds for transmission.

5.3. Requirements for CCAM Messages

This section describes the CCAM Messages used for each of the different Use Cases. It provides a first insight into the messages used and defines the basis for future development within the use cases. It furthermore harmonizes the messages with already existing standards and existing specifications.

It was decided that the specifications from C-Roads and Car2Car Communication Consortium are added as use case specific requirements; This is because pilots, which are being developed upon already existing infrastructure, would need to adjust their setup with a lot of effort to change the messages already deployed even if the existing infrastructure is not part of the Podium Use Cases. Nevertheless, PoDIUM does want to use the specifications and show the interoperability to those specifications being part of the current deployment of C-ITS within Europe and also describe Use Cases which are part of PoDIUM Use Cases.

5.3.1. General CCAM Message Requirements

Table 32: General CCAM message requirements

ID	Description
CCAM_1	CAM messages shall be based on the ETSI EN 302 637-2 V1.4.1
CCAM_2	VAM shall be based on ETSI TS 103 300-3 V2.1.2
CCAM_3	CDD shall be based on ETSI TS 102 894-2 V1.2.1
CCAM_3	DENM shall be based on ETSI EN 302 637-3 V.1.3.1
CCAM_4	IVIM shall be based on ETSI TS 103 301 V1.3.1
CCAM_5	CPM shall be based on ETSI TR 103 562 V2.1.1 or newer.
CCAM_6	SPATEM shall be based on ETSI TS 103 301 v1.3.1
CCAM_7	MAPEM shall be based on ETSI TS 103 301 v1.3.1
CCAM_8	Short range Communication shall be using either IST-G5, C-V2X, 60GHz Wifi or a combination of those.
CCAM_9	Long Range communication shall use 4G or 5G cellular Networks

5.3.2. Use case-specific CCAM message requirements

5.3.2.1. Use Case 2

Table 33: UC2 CCAM message requirements

ID	Description
CCAM_UC2_1	DENM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.

5.3.2.2. Use Case 3

Table 34: UC3 CCAM message requirements

ID	Description
CCAM_UC3_1	DENM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.
CCAM_UC3_2	MCM shall be based on ETSI TS 103 561 v0.0.2 or the newest version available during the implementation phase.

5.3.2.3. Use Case 4

Table 35: UC4 CCAM message requirements

ID	Description
CCAM_UC4_1	CAM Messages send from a vehicle shall be based on the Car 2 Car Communication Consortium Basic System Profile v1.6.3 or higher for already existing vehicle use cases.
CCAM_UC4_2	DENM Messages send from a vehicle shall be based on the Car 2 Car Communication Consortium Basic System Profile v1.6.3 or higher for already existing vehicle use cases.
CCAM_UC4_3	DENM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.
CCAM_UC4_4	IVIM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.
CCAM_UC4_5	SPATEM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.
CCAM_UC4_6	MAPEM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.

5.3.2.4. Use Case 5

Table 36: UC5 CCAM message requirements

ID	Description
CCAM_UC5_1	CAM Messages send from a vehicle shall be based on the Car 2 Car Communication Consortium Basic System Profile v1.6.3 or higher for already existing vehicle use cases.
CCAM_UC5_2	DENM Messages send from a vehicle shall be based on the Car 2 Car Communication Consortium Basic System Profile v1.6.3 or higher for already existing vehicle use cases.
CCAM_UC5_3	DENM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.
CCAM_UC5_4	IVIM shall be based on the C-Roads Specification for already existing infrastructure related Use Cases.

5.3.3. CCAM Message Security

To ensure trust between infrastructure and vehicles of the different involved parties the EU defined several rules and standards which CCAM Messages need to obey if they want to be understood and used by the different parties. As in PoDIUM the focus in several use cases aim not to inform different parties but mostly aim to proof a concept and investigate its feasibility, the security is not necessarily needed in the different use cases and can therefore be omitted. Nevertheless, in Use Cases which use CCAM Message security, these requirements shall apply.

Table 37: CCAM message security requirements

ID	Description
CCAM_SEC_1	Messages shall be secured with ETSI 103 097 v1.3.1 or higher.
CCAM_SEC_2	Messages shall be secured with ETCL L0 certificates.
CCAM_SEC_3	Messages security shall follow the current valid Security Policy during implementation (currently release 1)
CCAM_SEC_4	Message security shall follow the current valid Certificate Policy during implementation (currently v1.1.)

5.4. Requirements for trust, security and privacy

5.4.1. Trusted computing approach

Any connected system can be modelled as a set of connected devices working on well-defined tasks; the outputs of some devices become inputs of others. The constant exchange of data between devices requires digital identity management and a secure communication protocol. These problems have

been already solved by (1) public key infrastructure (PKI) based on X.509 certificates, and (2) the Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol. The combination of the two solutions provides authentication of the devices and confidentiality and integrity of the exchanged data.

These two solutions allow any device of the connected system to authenticate the devices willing to connect and then to protect the data in transit over the communication channel. However, these solutions do not cope with increasing software attacks, *i.e.*, attacks that leverage the attack surface of devices to intentionally modify the behaviour of the code and/or modify the data before transmission over the TLS channel. For example, bad actors can attack the applications (or the configuration files) to intercept/modify the data before secure transmission, or even change the bootloader to boot an untrusted operating system.

To overcome these issues, the Trusting Computing Group (TCG), a not-for-profit organization formed to develop, define, and promote open standards for the Trusted Computing approach based on a hardware-based root of trust [10]. Trusted Computing (TC) is a set of interoperable technologies to achieve a level of trust in the behaviour of a device. The core element of TC is the hardware Root of Trust called Trusted Platform Module (TPM) a tamper-resistant cryptographic hardware integrated with the system board that implements primitive cryptographic functions on top of which more complex features can be built following TCG specification TPM 2.0 [1]. The objective of TC is to enable devices to measure and prove their integrity cryptographically, *i.e.*, prove that their running software is the intended one and it has not been tampered. Integrity measurement is therefore the process the devices adopt to collect and digest the information about the integrity of their software and configuration to be attested/verified. The four main hardware Roots of Trust to make the node a Trusted Computing Base (TCB) are:

- **Core Root of Trust for Measurements (CRTM):** commonly implemented by the initial bootloader secure code executed at power-up or hardware reset.
- **Root of Trust for Storage (RTS):** the TPM that provides:
 - a set of Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs) to securely accumulate the integrity measurements in the form of hashes, and
 - a key hierarchy architecture to securely store objects protected via encryption by the TPM on the file system.
- **Root of Trust for Reporting (RTR):** the TPM that signs the values of a PCR set using an Attestation Key bound to the Endorsement Key, *i.e.*, a resident key that represents the TPM identity and that guarantees the origin and the integrity of the PCR values shared for attestation.

The principles of Trusted Computing can also be applied to Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS). Such a connected system is modelled by interconnected devices that rely on others to take decisions, even critical ones, installed into: Vehicles with many ECUs controlled by a central OBU; Roadside units that provide services to the passing vehicles, and MEC servers. Applying the principle of Trusted Computing is critical to building trust among those devices and avoid exchange of incorrect or malicious information over secure protocols. Figure 9 depicts how PoDIUM will explore and experiment with the TC principles based on TPM Root of Trust to measure and verify the firmware integrity, hence, to protect the overall system from attacks targeting the integrity of OBU and RSU software at boot and runtime.

Figure 9: Chain of automotive attestation

Each vehicle is modelled by its OBU; RSUs acts as Remote Attestors and they verify the integrity of the OBU of passing vehicles, through Remote Attestation protocol. Moreover, exploiting the same TPM approach, a dedicated service on MEC servers can challenge both OBUs and RSUs. The approach is designed to build trust among all devices, so that they may rely on data coming from the field.

The trust and security requirements for implementing this solution are listed below with a brief explanation.

Table 38 Trust and Security Requirements

ID	Description
P_SEC_TC_001	On-Board Units (OBUs) and Road-Side Units (RSUs) must act as Trusted Computing Bases (TCB)
P_SEC_TC_002	The TCBs must possess a Core Root of Trust for Measurements (CRTM), i.e., Trust Anchor, in the form of the internal ROM code that must be trusted.
P_SEC_TC_003	The TCBs must possess a Root of Trust for Measurements (RTM), i.e., the CPU controlled by the CRTM.
P_SEC_TC_004	The TCBs must possess a Root of Trust for Storage (RTS), i.e., TPM that provides a set of Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs) to securely store (accumulate) the integrity measurements.
P_SEC_TC_005	The TCBs must possess a Root of Trust for Reporting (RTR), i.e., TPM that is able to sign the values of a PCR set.
P_SEC_TC_006	The TCBs should possess a trusted bootloader with TPM support.
P_SEC_TC_007	The TCBs must block the ability to clear TPM.
P_SEC_TC_008	The TCBs must enable the Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) in their Linux Kernel.
P_SEC_TC_009	The TCBs must implement a policy to measure the integrity of all relevant files.
P_SEC_TC_010	The TCBs must implement a policy to measure the integrity of all relevant files running in a container.

This set of requirements makes OBUs and RSUs compliant to the definition of TCBs. As described earlier, a TCB consists of a set of CRTM, RTS and RTR a condition partially satisfied by the presence of the CPU, bootloader and the TPM2.0. The TPM2.0 stores the integrity measures taken during the chain of trust building process and it is challenged by a remote attester to prove the integrity of the software running on the platform. The possibility of resetting the TPM must be blocked to avoid the irreparable loss of sensitive info. A TCB also possesses SW requirements. The bootloader must have TPM support to save the measurements taken even before the kernel and drivers are loaded and executed. During the attestation phase it will be possible to know exactly which version of the software was executed before the kernel, in line with the principle of Trusted Computing. The Linux kernel must enable the Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) module [11], a security subsystem of the Linux kernel that measures the integrity of files based on a user-defined policy. The policy is defined based on files to be verified and must support the case of applications/services running in containers.

Table 39 TCB Trust and Security Requirements

ID	Description
P_SEC_TC_011	TCBs leverage software integrity verification at boot and trigger the proper countermeasures in the event of violations
P_SEC_TC_012	The TCBs developer must sign the bootloader.
P_SEC_TC_013	The TCBs developer must sign the Linux kernel.
P_SEC_TC_014	The TCBs must check the software authenticity before loading the bootloader and, in case of violation, it must stop the bootstrap.
P_SEC_TC_015	The TCBs must check the software authenticity before loading the kernel, in case of violation, it must stop the bootstrap.

This set of requirements deals with the boot phase of TCBs. The TCBs need to be able to verify the integrity of the software that is loaded during the boot phase and make trust decisions, *i.e.*, decide whether to continue or block the boot phase. In addition, the SW must be authentic, *i.e.*, only SW created and signed by the developer must run on the TCBs.

Table 40 Attester Trust and Security Requirements

ID	Description
P_SEC_TC_016	The attester node (RSU or MEC Server) must be able to challenge the TCBs (OBUs and RSUs) for verifying their trust status
P_SEC_TC_017	The attester node must possess a list of valid integrity values for files running on TCBs (<i>i.e.</i> , Golden Values).
P_SEC_TC_018	The attester node must know the identity of the TCBs (<i>i.e.</i> , its public key certificate).
P_SEC_TC_019	The attester node must be able to establish a (secure) communication channel with the TCBs before challenging their trust status.
P_SEC_TC_020	The attester node must implement an attestation protocol that queries the RTR of TCBs and checks the integrity value of the files against its Golden Values.

P_SEC_TC_021	The attesor node must activate appropriate countermeasures in case of violation of TCBS file integrity detected during the attestation protocol.
P_SEC_TC_022	When and where possible software integrity verification should be implemented in a privacy-preserving manner.

This set of requirements for the remote attesor (RSU and MEC server) are necessary to run the remote attestation protocol and assess the trust status of the TCBS. The attesor is responsible for checking the integrity values of the code executed on the TCBS against the expected values to assess that the system has not been attacked and the trust status is valid. To do this, the attesor must have a list of valid values called Golden Values and must also know the identity of the TCBS in the form of a certified public key used. The attesor must implement a remote attestation protocol that queries the TCBS about their trust status, possibly implemented in a way that preserves TCBS privacy. If any value is different from its Golden Value, the remote attesor must trigger the proper countermeasure.

Table 41 RSUs and OBUs' Trust and Security Requirements

ID	Description
P_SEC_TC_023	OBUs and RSUs must have their own digital identity in accordance with X.509-base PKI
P_SEC_TC_024	The OBUs and RSUs must possess a key pair linked to their digital identity.
P_SEC_TC_025	The OBUs and RSUs must create the key pair using the TPM and the private key must never leave it.
P_SEC_TC_026	The OBUs and RSUs must possess a public certificate certifying possession of the public key issued by a third-party trusted entity.
P_SEC_TC_027	The OBUs and RSUs must possess an Attestation Key (AK) created using TPM from Endorsement Key (EK).
P_SEC_TC_028	The OBUs and RSUs must possess a public certificate certifying possession of the AK public key issued by a third-party trusted entity.
P_SEC_TC_029	The public certificates must follow the form of the x509 certificate.
P_SEC_TC_030	The OBUs and RSUs must be able to prove their identity to other nodes.
P_SEC_TC_031	All nodes must be able to verify the validity of the OBUs and RSUs public certificates.
P_SEC_TC_032	The OBUs and RSUs must be able to prove their identity to other nodes.

Establishing a TLS channel between RSUs and OBUs for integrity, confidentiality, and (mutual) authentication purposes before proceeding with remote attestation [15].

Table 42 Application Data Security

ID	Description
P_SEC_TC_035	Critical application data must be protected through encryption using a key residing in the TPM (TPM Sealing).

The principle of trusted computing ensures data integrity but not data confidentiality. Applications, however, may need confidentiality. The TPM 2.0 permits to store inside its non-volatile memory, small data or key to encrypt large data (TPM Sealing/Unsealing).

The requirements previously discussed drive the design of the Software Integrity Architecture of the TCB. The overall Software Integrity Architecture is depicted in Figure 10. The resulting internal architecture is responsible for building the Chain of Trust and enabling 3 trust decisions, two at boot time (on the integrity of bootloader and then on Linux kernel) and one at runtime (on the integrity of applications/services) through periodic remote attestation.

Figure 10 : Software Integrity Architecture

The identification of the software components is performed through a Chain of Trust, *i.e.*, a hierarchy of trust rooted in a Trust Anchor (TA). The TA is an authoritative entity for which trust is assumed and not derived, *i.e.*, a small and carefully designed piece of firmware, executed by the system at power-up or hardware reset. The TA is responsible for starting the Chain of Trust during the bootstrap of the TCB. Each element of the chain is a software component that, when executed, performs its tasks and then identifies, loads, and finally executes the next software component (see Figure 11). The identification of a component is made of two steps: the measurement, *i.e.*, a digest, calculated over that component, and the storage of such measurement in the TPM, *i.e.*, the accumulation of the measurement via PCR extension operation. Each PCR can contain one digest value, which is the result of one or more PCR extension operations: $PCR_{i+1} = PCR_i || hash(component)$. It is not possible to store a value directly in a PCR, but the only way to access a PCR for writing is through the PCR extend operation: this guarantees that all measurements are accumulated.

Figure 11: Basic procedure of building a Chain of Trust.

By building on the fact that the Trust Anchor (TA) is trusted, and each software component is considered trusted at least to identify the next component, the identification of all components is trusted as well due to the transitive property of trust. The bootstrap process enhanced to build the Chain of Trust, *i.e.*, the capability of each software component to identify and load the next one, is called Authenticated Boot(strap) and goes from the TA up to the applications/services in user space through bootloader and Linux kernel. Through measurement control, it is possible to stop the loading of a component if an unexpected component is detected through a Trust Decision, a decision whether a platform can be considered trusted for an intended purpose or not. It builds upon the Authenticated Boot, can occur (at any meaningful time) during it or after it, and implies the cryptographic verification of the loaded software components to identify them and verify that they are the expected ones. If the Trust Decision is taken during the bootstrap, the verification is performed by the platform itself (usually using the TPM) over the components loaded until the decision time: based on the result of the verification, the bootstrap process can be stopped. This portion of the Authenticated Boot(strap) is called Secure Boot(strap). The verification is performed also after the bootstrap completion and it is called Remote Attestation: a remote entity, the Attestor, with a given periodicity challenges and verifies the trustworthiness of target device with the support of the trusted component on the platform, *i.e.*, the TPM that provides the measures of loaded/run component, to be checked against a whitelist of correct values called Golden Value.

5.4.2. Data and Data Source Reliability approach

Once a cryptographic trust in the sources and their data is built by means of trust computing approach, a further subjective trust in data coming from different sources can be considered. PoDIUM will experiment two different approaches; these approaches are present in UC1 and UC4 respectively.

Approach 1: the reliability of information sources or the respective received data from these sources is assessed for trust-building by means of integrating subjective logic-based reliability estimation schemes into the data processing chain of at least the MEC server. The underlying idea is to build figures of merit for all contributing sources to set up a meaningful environment model.

The following table show the list of requirements:

Table 43 Data and data source reliability - Approach 1

ID	Description	Motivation
P_SEC_UC1_001	A model of the normal behaviour of information sources is available at the MEC.	The normal behaviour will be needed to assess possible malfunctions or errors.
P_SEC_UC1_002	The data can be linked to the originating source and it can be processed on the MEC before it is integrated into the digital twin.	The reliability estimation needs to link information to the originating sources and process it before the

		data is integrated into an overall model.
P_SEC_UC1_002	The digital twin module is able to gainfully use the additional reliability information when fusing data from different sources.	The output of the reliability estimation should be used by the environment model building block to make the digital twin more meaningful.

Approach 2: The reliability of the information grows as the redundancy of the originating data is achieved; redundancy is the key to build an indicator of truthfulness of the data; an event detection or object is introduced into the platform in a MEC or Cloud service attached to an indicator of the redundancy indicating how many sources are supporting such information. The current state of the art in object detection techniques recognizes the importance of leveraging redundant sensors to enhance accuracy. By integrating redundant sensors into the detection system, it becomes possible to capture a more comprehensive and robust representation of the surrounding environment. This redundancy provides the opportunity to cross-validate information from multiple sensor inputs, reducing the likelihood of false positives or false negatives. The following table shows the list of requirements:

Table 44 Data and data source reliability - Approach 2

ID	Description	Motivation
P_SEC_UC4_001	Data introduced in the platform are ranked with an indicator of redundancy	State of the art object detection supports the usage of redundant sensors in order to improve accuracy
P_SEC_UC4_002	The system will use redundancy in order to build up certainty of the information used into the platform	According to t ETSI EN 302 637-3 V1.2.1 section B.23 establishes information quality as a measure of the probability of the information to be certain.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, this document provides the platform requirements identified and specified for the PoDIUM project.

The identification of the platform requirements has been based on the detailed specification of the use cases and the high-level requirements derived in T2.1, the further work on specifying the PoDIUM platform requirements as part of T2.2, the analysis of CCAM messages requirements in T2.3 and the security requirements and specifications coming from T2.4. This task was performed by a multisourcing methodology that used several sources of information for the PoDIUM requirements specification.

The requirements definition for the networking domain followed an identification of use case types coming from widely accepted bibliography, as described in section 3. In parallel, for all the other domains the requirements were specified by identifying and characterizing the overall system functionalities and the interactions among the system components.

7. References

1. Trust Computing Group (2019), "Trusted Platform Module Library Part 1: Architecture", https://trustedcomputinggroup.org/wp-content/uploads/TCG_TPM2_r1p59_Part1_Architecture_pub.pdf
2. 3GPP TR 22.885 V14.0.0 (2015-12), "3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Study on LTE support for Vehicle to Everything (V2X) services (Release 14)".
3. 3GPP TR 22.886 V16.2.0 (2018-12), "3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Study on enhancement of 3GPP Support for 5G V2X Services (Release 16)".
4. 3GPP TS 22.185 V16.0.0 (2020-07), "3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Service requirements for V2X services; Stage 1 (Release 16)".
5. 3GPP TS 22.186 V16.2.0 (2019-06), "3rd Generation Partnership Project; Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Enhancement of 3GPP support for V2X scenarios; Stage 1 (Release 16)".
6. ETSI TR 102 638 V1.1.1 (2009-06), "[Intelligent Transport Systems \(ITS\); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Definitions](#)".
7. 5GAA (2020), "C-V2X Use Cases and Service Level Requirements Volume I", https://5gaa.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/5GAA_T-200111_TR_C-V2X_Use_Cases_and_Service_Level_Requirements_Vol_I-V3.pdf
8. 5GAA (2020), "C-V2X Use Cases Volume II: Examples and Service Level Requirements", https://5gaa.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/5GAA_White-Paper_C-V2X-Use-Cases-Volume-II.pdf
9. CAR 2 CAR Communication Consortium (2019), "Guidance for day 2 and beyond roadmap", https://www.car-2-car.org/fileadmin/documents/General_Documents/C2CCC_WP_2072_RoadmapDay2AndBeyond.pdf
10. Trusted computing group (2023), <https://trustedcomputinggroup.org>
11. linux-ima (2014), "Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA)", <https://sourceforge.net/p/linux-ima/wiki/Home>
12. https://trustedcomputinggroup.org/wp-content/uploads/TCG-EK-Credential-Profile-V-2.5-R2_published.pdf
13. Trusted Computing Group, (2021), "Keys for device identity and attestation", https://trustedcomputinggroup.org/wp-content/uploads/TPM-2p0-Keys-for-Device-Identity-and-Attestation_v1_r12_pub10082021.pdf
14. ETSI, (2020), "Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS); Security; Trust and Privacy Management; Release 2", https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/102900_102999/102941/02.02.01_60/ts_102941v020201p.pdf
15. <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc8446>
16. Sensors (2021), p. 159, "Collective Perception: A Safety Perspective", <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/1/159>

8. Annex: Classification of networking vehicular use case categories related to PODIUM

Connectivity is a major feature of the PoDIUM architecture. Given the rich existing bibliography on the networking requirements of CCAM services (e.g., [7], [8]), we performed a classification of the main vehicular use cases. Similar use cases are grouped together to ease the analysis. Then, by identifying the most relevant category for each PoDIUM use case/service, we were able to derive an initial set of networking requirements for our PoDIUM services, which were then elaborated and adjusted to capture the specifics of PoDIUM UCs. In this annex, we present the results of the initial classification, which could be of use to other related projects.

8.1. Road safety

This category of use cases is mainly related to the signalling of events and to the provision of information that can increase the road safety. Two main types of information and events can be identified for the road safety use cases. This distinction has been made because the requirements of these two groups of use cases are different due to the different characteristics of the information and events to be signalled.

The first type concerns static or periodical information and events that are known to the roadside infrastructure or that have been identified exploiting roadside or in-vehicle sensors. This type of information concerns road information and events that represent dangerous situations for the vehicle's driving, such as weather, roadworks, traffic or road conditions.

The second type of road safety use cases are instead related to dynamic events that are identified by sensors or by application exploiting available data in real-time. These events are mainly related to the dynamics of the vehicles and of the other road actors (e.g., VRU). In this sub-category, there are included use cases such as collision warning, electronic emergency brake warning, wrong way driving or vulnerable road user warning.

8.1.1. Requirements of use cases related to static information

A connected vehicle can be informed about the static information and events from a backend application, that resides either at the edge or at the cloud of the communication network, or from another connected vehicle, that is aware of the event thanks to its sensors (e.g., the vehicle detects bad road surface conditions or puddles).

If the message is provided by the backend, the maximum acceptable latency is in the order of 1-2 seconds based on the analysis of both 3GPP and 5GAA. If the message is sent using direct vehicular communication by another vehicle or RSU, the latency required must be below 100 ms. This strict limit has been set since it is assumed that vehicle can be at high speed and it needs to have the time to react to the warning since the hazardous event is likely to be within 300 meters of range, that is the typical communication distance of V2X transmission.

The message size in both cases is typically around 300 bytes (i.e., the average size of a CAM or DENM message) with a maximum estimated size of 1000 bytes. These messages can contain information about the event providing some details and the location. However, there is no need to provide very detailed information or raw data.

The reliability is requested to be at the 99%. The warnings are about events that concern the road safety, and it is necessary to have reliable communication. Few losses are in any case acceptable since

the warning messages are periodically repeated and a loss can be recovered by a following transmission.

8.1.2. Requirements of use cases related to dynamic information

The latency required for these use cases is set to 100 ms in both 3GPP and 5GAA analysis. Some specific events may require a lower latency limit to ensure a better reaction. For example, in the list of potential requirements of the “*pre-crash sensing warning*” use case in the 3GPP TR a latency of 20 ms is indicated. Instead, the 5GAA analysis recommends that the communication latency should be 20 ms for “*VRU warning*” use case since the presence of VRU is typical signalled when very close to the vehicle.

In general, the information about dynamic road safety related events should be transferred as soon as possible, but the 100 ms threshold is considered to be low enough for the majority of the use cases. Some slightly variations may in any case be introduced for some use cases. For example, the 5GAA analysis estimates that for the “*electronic emergency brake*” use case the latency requirement should be set equal to 120 ms to be comparable to the performance of other anti-collision system (e.g., radar, image-based system).

The vehicular applications of several of these use cases exploit the position and dynamics information of vehicles contained in the received CAM messages to detect possible hazardous events (e.g., collision, emergency brake). Alternatively, the vehicle or the roadside infrastructure that detect the events can generate a DENM message to warn the involved vehicles about the possible danger. The amount of information to be exchanged is the typical size of a CAM or DENM message (i.e., about 300 bytes). The network shall support a high transmit frequency of these messages up to a maximum of 10 messages per second. A vehicle requires then an upload bandwidth of few tens of kbps.

The reliability to be ensured for the transmission in these use cases must be very high (99.99%) as they concern safety critical events.

8.2. Cooperative driving

The cooperative driving use cases comprise two main types of actions. One concerns the exchange of information about trajectories, dynamics, current and planned manoeuvres, the other is related to the sharing of sensors’ data. Here we report the requirements for these two types of actions separately because some of them change significantly according to the operation to be performed. These two actions are not mutually exclusive, but, depending on the use case, both actions or just one of the two are performed.

8.2.1. Manoeuvres coordination

We refer to “manoeuvres coordination” to all those interactions among vehicles, and among vehicles and roadside infrastructure that are performed for defining and agreeing cooperatively the future trajectories of the vehicles in a local road segment (e.g., an intersection, a merging lane). In this context, we consider also platooning and tele-operated driving as some peculiar cases of manoeuvres coordination.

8.2.2. Cooperative Manoeuvres Coordination requirements

The interactions of cooperative manoeuvres coordination use cases include the sharing of the desired and planned trajectories of the vehicle, the feedbacks received from the other vehicle and the decision

process to agree on the manoeuvres to be performed. The 5GAA analysis estimated that the overall interactions may consist in an amount of information of about 50 Kbytes. This is the amount of information that should be exchanged between a pair of vehicles. It is necessary to consider that more vehicles are present in the same area. In an urban environment, the study of 5GAA estimated about 300 vehicles within a communication range of 100 meters exchanging manoeuvres information each 5 seconds. This means a bandwidth of about 24 Mbps. Instead, in a highway environment, a larger communication range of 500 meters is set and a transmission frequency of 10 seconds is considered. This results in a higher required bandwidth of 64 Mbps. These values are confirmed also by the 3GPP TS even if less details are provided, and the required bandwidth values is considering together the transmission of cooperative manoeuvres of perception data from sensors.

Other information to be transferred need to be considered in the case that the manoeuvres coordination is performed by a roadside entity in charge of managing an intersection crossing. In this specific use case, we need to consider that CAM messages from each vehicle are sent with a maximum frequency of 10 Hz and average size of 300 bytes, SPATEM and MAPEM messages are sent to provide respectively traffic lights information (~ 100 bytes) and details about the topology of the intersection (~ 1000 bytes). MAPEM messages are typical sent at frequency of 1 second, SPATEM may vary from 1 second to more times at seconds in some use cases. Finally, information about the planned trajectories to each vehicle is sent from the intersection manager. This information may account for about 400 bytes for each vehicle.

The latency requirement is dependent on the information to be shared. In case of cooperative manoeuvres to avoid collisions or to change lane with high level of automation, it is essential to have very short delay. The 3GPP documents specify that a 10 ms latency is required for these situations. Instead, the information sharing among automated vehicles with a low level of automation can have less strict constraints. A latency up to 100 ms is acceptable. The 5GAA analysis provides similar latency requirements. They are in a range from 80 up to 160 ms depending on the specific use case considered. Only exception is when the manoeuvres coordination at an intersection is performed by an intersection controller. In that specific case, a latency of 10 ms is required since the intersection controller may send information at the last instant and vehicles should receive as soon as possible that information for a prompt reaction.

The reliability requirement needs to be very high since the loss of information highly impacts on the manoeuvres coordination process resulting in significant risks for the vehicles involved. The analysis of 5GAA indicates a reliability of 99.9 % for cooperative driving use cases, 3GPP TS do not specify any value to most of the considered cases indicating that a sufficient reliability should be provided. It just specifies that a 99.999% reliability shall be ensured for emergency trajectories definition and 99.99% reliability for the highest level of automation.

8.2.3. Platooning requirements

The platooning use case has some specific requirements since the vehicles involved in a platoon coordinate among themselves in a different way with respect to a general manoeuvres coordination use case. Indeed, in a platoon the leading vehicle shares the information to manage the platoon, while the other members of the platoon typically share only their position, dynamics, and acceleration/deceleration intentions.

The requirements specified by 3GPP and the ones provided in the 5GAA study are quite different. The different platooning scenarios that have been considered are significantly influencing the latency requirements. The 3GPP document considers indeed two platooning scenarios. In one scenario, that has been defined as normal density scenario, the distance between vehicles is of 2 meters or larger. In the second scenario, the distance between vehicles is only of 1 meter to represent a high-density

scenario. Instead, in the 5GAA analysis a range from 5 up to 15 meters has been considered as inter-vehicle distance.

The distance between vehicle is significantly impacting on the required message latency and on the frequency of message transmission. Shorter is the distance between vehicles, lower is the required latency and higher is the message transmission frequency. The 3GPP TS indeed specifies that the required latency shall be in the range from 10 ms for the highest level of automation up to 25 ms for the lowest level and the frequency of messages shall be 30 times per second. The latency requirement indicated by the 5GAA study is instead less strict. It is from 50 up to 100 ms according to the platoon interactions performed. A frequency of 10 Hz for the exchanges of messages within the platoon is sufficient.

The size of messages to be transmitted is in the same range in both 3GPP and 5GAA documents. Messages are typically within the range from 100 up to 400 bytes. When perception sensors data is sent the message size can increase up to 6500 bytes according to 3GPP specifications.

The reliability is considered crucial. 5GAA states that a 99.9% of reliability is required, while 3GPP expects an even higher reliability of 99.99% for the highest level of automation.

In the platooning scenario, a communication flow between the leading vehicle and a backend application at the edge/cloud or at an RSU is also expected. This flow is used to report road status information that the platoon gathered to the backend application and it is also used by the leading vehicle to receive information about weather and road conditions. The requirements of this communication flow are less strict since it is not critical for the platooning operations. A latency of 500 ms up to 1 second is acceptable with a 99% message transmission reliability. A data rate below 10 kbps can be assumed as requirement taking into account that this information is not periodically exchanged, but it is event-driven.

8.2.4. Tele-operated driving

We consider as tele-operated driving those use cases in which a human remote driver provides the commands (e.g., turn steering wheel, brake pressure) to the vehicle for all driving operations. The remote driver exploits video streaming information from the camera on-board of the vehicle to define the commands to send. The requirements of video-streaming are introduced in the subsection devoted to sensor sharing. In the following of this subsection, we highlight the requirements of the communication flow from the remote driver to the vehicle. This choice has been made since requirements of video streaming are different from communication commands flow and they are more similar to those of other use cases in which data from sensors are shared among different road actors.

The requirements of this use case are strictly related to the maximum speed at which the vehicle can drive. In the 3GPP specification, it is noted that the network system shall support a maximum vehicle speed of 250 km/h. This corresponds to a general maximum vehicle speed and not to the maximum achievable speed for tele-operated driving application. In any case, the 3GPP requirements are equal to a maximum latency of 5 ms and a download bandwidth of 1 Mbps. The 5GAA study is instead considering a vehicle speed of 50 km/h. The requirements at this speed are a latency of 20 ms and a maximum download bandwidth of 400 kbps.

A reliability of 99.999% is required since the vehicle completely relies on the commands sent from the remote driver for performing any driving actions. No losses are admitted since they can significantly affect the safety of the vehicle and of its passengers.

8.3. Sensors sharing requirements

The sharing of information from sensors can be of two types: 1) the sharing of processed data (i.e., list of objects with a set of attributes), 2) raw sensors data. Requirements are significantly different for these two cases. Raw data can include data from LiDAR and from RADAR sensors, but they mainly consist in video streaming from cameras.

In the case that processed data are shared, 3GPP specifies that a size of message equal to 1600 byte shall be supported. A maximum message frequency of 10 Hz shall be foreseen. This results in a rate of about 128 kbps. A maximum size of 1000 byte is instead indicated by the 5GAA study for the transmission of processed sensors data.

The requirements for processed data transmission for 3GPP are indicated for the lower levels of automation. Thus, not tight requirements have been fixed for both latency (100 ms) and for reliability (99%). On the contrary, the 5GAA study considers the sharing of processed data as a critical process that requires very low latency (10 ms) and high reliability (99.9%), to ensure sufficient quality of service and timely information to the vehicles. These requirements depend essentially on how the data are thought to be exploited by the vehicles.

The 3GPP TS introduces requirements for more advanced sensors data sharing. These data can be low-resolution or raw data that can be exploited to reach higher level of automation. Due to the more challenging scope, requirements are much stricter than in the previous case. The latency shall be 3 ms in the worst case and the transmission shall support a bandwidth up to 50 Mbps with a 99.999% reliability.

Some specific requirements are provided for video sharing in the 5GAA study. These requirements are significantly influenced by the number of cameras to be used, the compression rate and the video resolution. These aspects are strictly related to the use cases to be analysed. For example, in the 5GAA study a single camera producing one flow of about 5 Mbps is expected to be used for “*obstructed view assist*” use case, while for the “*tele-operated driving*” use case 4 high-definition cameras (one on each side of the vehicle) are required resulting in a total requirement of 32 Mbps upload bandwidth. The 3GPP specifies for video sharing a wide upload bandwidth range to be supported that starts from 10 Mbps and it arrives up to 700 Mbps.

The reliability of the 5GAA mentioned use cases is of 99% to avoid large artefacts that may compromise the usefulness of the video. In these use cases, the video is mainly used by a human driver. Instead, 3GPP defines a higher reliability equal to 99.99% considering autonomous driving cars with high level of automation. High reliability is required to avoid possible errors that may compromise the correct working of computer image algorithms. A latency of 10 ms is required for the higher level of automations, while 50 ms for the lower ones or where a human driver is involved.

A peculiar use case about sensors sharing has been introduced in the 5GAA study. The use case is “*high-definition map collecting and sharing*” case. Some specific requirements about LiDAR and other sensors data different from video streaming have been introduced for this use case and they can be taken as reference to other use cases involving the exchange of similar information. Furthermore, the 5GAA study provides bandwidth requirements for both processed and raw sensors data. A requirement of 4 Mbps for the exchanges of processed sensors data is indicated. It has been considered that the information to be transmitted is strictly dependent on the number of objects in the surrounding environment. The 4 Mbps bandwidth has been estimated considering on average 50 objects and for each of them 1 Kbytes of information should be provided each 100 ms. This bandwidth requirement is higher with respect to the previously since more detailed information about each object are required to build high-definition maps. Instead, the bandwidth requirements for sharing raw

sensors data has been fixed to 47 Mbps, considering a camera (about 8 Mbps), a LiDAR (35 Mbps) and data from other sensors. A latency of 100 ms is expected to guarantee that the high-definition map can be used in real-time. A reliability of 99 % is indicated as acceptable for this specific use case.

8.4. Traffic management

Traffic management use cases mainly involve the provision of position and dynamics of vehicles to edge/cloud applications that can provide indications to the vehicles about routes to follow.

This information can be sent from vehicles to traffic management applications using CAM-like messages with a typical size of 300 bytes. Additional data, such as destination, may be sent, but it is not significantly impacting on the bandwidth requirement. This information can be transmitted just once when starting the application. The information about routes suggestions that traffic management applications sent to vehicles can be quantified in the order of maximum 300 bytes. The needed frequency of transmission of these messages can be lower with respect to road safety use case. A maximum frequency of 1 Hz can be set as requirement in most of the use cases in this category. The bandwidth requirement can then be assumed to be of few kbps.

Latency is not critical for these use cases. It mainly depends on the amount of time that drivers or autonomous driving vehicles need to implement the driving action (e.g., change route) suggested by the traffic management application. Values of latency in the range from 500 ms up to 3 seconds are acceptable depending on the considered use cases.

A 95% reliability is set as requirement since the information is not safety critical and a high reliability is not strictly required. However, the communication flow needs a sufficient reliability to ensure that the users can experience an adequate level of performance.

Table 45: Communication requirements for the different use cases categories

Use cases		Latency	Information exchanged	Reliability
Road safety use cases	Static events	100 ms V2V 1-2 s V2N	1-10 kbps	99%
	Dynamic events	20-100 ms	20-30 kbps	99.99%
Cooperative Driving	Manoeuvres coordination	Cooperative Manoeuvres Coordination	10/100 ms high/low automation level	25-65 Mbps 99.99%
		Platooning	10-100 ms V2V 500 ms - 1 s V2N	30-100 kbps V2V < 10 kbps V2N 99.99%
		Tele-operated	5-20 ms	400 kbps - 1 Mbps 99.999%
	Sensors sharing	Processed data	10/100 ms high/low automation level	128 kbps/4 Mbps low/high quality 99.9%
		Raw data	3 ms	50 Mbps 99.999%
		Video data	10 ms high automation level 50 ms human driver/low	32-700 Mbps for self-driving cars 5-32 Mbps for human driver 99.99% for self-driving cars 99% for human driver

			automation level		
Driver comfort			500 ms - 2 s	< 10 kbps	95%
Vehicle status monitoring			30 s - not real-time	< 1 kbps for specific sensors ~20 kbps for all main sensors 1-10 Mbps for perception sensors not in real-time	99.99%
Traffic management			500 ms - 3 s	< 10 kbps	95%
Road infrastructure planning			not real-time	< 10 kbps 1-10 Mbps for perception sensors not in real-time	95%
Driver-aware service	<i>Informational and usage-based services</i>		< 5 s	< 10 kbps	90%
	<i>In-vehicle entertainment</i>	Online gaming / virtual reality	20 ms	250 Mbps	99%
		Video streaming and conferencing	150 ms	50 Mbps	90%